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Larval habitat modification and manipulation to control malaria: a systematic review

Authors

Elisa Martello, Gowsika Yogeswaran, Jo Leonardi-Bee

Contact

gmpfeedback@who.int

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1 **Larval habitat modification and manipulation to control malaria (Review)**

2 Elisa Martello¹, Gowsika Yogeswaran¹, Jo Leonardi-Bee¹

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4 ¹Centre for Evidence Based Healthcare, Division of Epidemiology and Public Health, Clinical Sciences
5 Building Phase 2, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, UK

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7 **EXTENDED ABSTRACT**

8

9 **Background:**

10 Malaria has a very high impact on public health, mostly on populations in Africa and Asia. Strategies to
11 control and reduce the burden have been studied for many years. More recently, integrated vector control
12 (IVC) strategies have been implemented to disrupt the disease transmission cycle. As a component of IVC,
13 larval source management (LSM) targeting larval habitats, could considerably limit the development of
14 juvenile stages, suppress the emerging adult populations and consequently contributing to reduce
15 parasite transmission. LSM activities may permanently or temporarily reduce the availability of larval
16 habitats (habitat modification and habitat manipulation, respectively), or involve addition of agents
17 (toxins, predators etc.) to water bodies to reduce the immature mosquito density.

18 **Objectives:** To describe and summarise the interventions of larval habitat modification and larval habitat
19 manipulation, and to assess the effects of habitat manipulation and habitat modification on malaria.

20

21 **Methods:**

22 *Search methods.* We searched six electronic databases (Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized
23 Register, MEDLINE, Embase, CAB Abstracts, and LILACS) and other relevant databases and grey literature
24 sources to October 2019.

25 *Selection criteria.* We conducted a systematic review of randomised controlled trials and non-randomised
26 intervention studies where larval source modification and/or manipulation was compared to no LSM
27 treatment or another active LSM intervention to evaluate the effects of the LSM interventions. We also
28 included uncontrolled before-after studies, but only described and summarized the interventions from
29 studies with these designs. We included studies irrespective of their publication status or language of
30 publication. Primary outcomes were clinical malaria incidence (critical outcome), malaria parasite
31 prevalence (critical outcome), and malaria parasitaemia incidence (important outcome). Secondary

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32 outcomes were incidence of severe malaria (critical outcome), anaemia prevalence, mean haemoglobin
33 levels, mortality rate due to malaria (important outcome), hospital admissions for malaria, density of
34 immature mosquitoes (important outcome), density of adult mosquitoes (important outcome),
35 sporozoite rate and entomological inoculation rate (EIR).

36 *Data collection and analysis.* Two authors independently screened titles and abstracts, and full texts
37 articles, extracted data and assessed risk of bias (using the Cochrane Risk of Bias 2.0 tool for randomised
38 trials and the ROBINS-I tool for non-randomised intervention studies). Any disagreements were resolved
39 by consensus or by a third reviewer. For all study designs, we used a narrative synthesis approach to
40 systematically describe and summarise all the interventions included within the review. The studies were
41 categorised by the type of intervention (habitat modification, habitat manipulation, combination of
42 habitat modification and manipulation) and the purpose of the intervention (LSM, non-LSM). Where
43 possible, the quantitative findings from all included studies, except those which used an uncontrolled
44 before-after design, were analysed to assess the effectiveness of the interventions. Meta-analysis was not
45 possible due to insufficient studies using the similar interventions. Grading of Recommendations,
46 Assessment, Development and Evaluations (GRADE) was used to assess the certainty of the evidence for
47 each intervention.

48

49 **Results:** Fifteen studies were included in the systematic review, and one on-going study was identified.
50 Of the included studies, five used a randomised controlled design (one used a parallel randomised
51 controlled trial design, four used a cluster-randomised controlled trial design), six used a controlled
52 before-after study design, three used a non-randomised controlled design, and one used an uncontrolled
53 before-after study design. Nine studies were conducted in Africa, five in Asia and the final study in Europe.
54 Eleven studies evaluated habitat manipulation using either water management (5 comparisons), shading
55 management (3 comparisons), other/combined management (3 comparisons) approaches. Four studies
56 evaluated a combination of habitat manipulation and modification. Three studies reported
57 epidemiological outcomes and 10 studies reported entomological outcomes. None of the studies reported
58 on the environmental impacts associated with the intervention. The overall risk of bias was 'high' for one
59 cluster-RCT and of 'some concerns' for the remaining three cluster-RCTs and individual RCT. For seven
60 studies using non-randomised intervention designs which reported outcome data, the overall risk of bias
61 was 'moderate' for two studies assessing two outcomes, and 'serious' for five studies reporting five
62 outcomes. The risk of bias for one further controlled before-after study and the uncontrolled before-after
63 study was 'critical'. The findings from the studies are presented by the different comparisons.

64 **Comparison 1. Habitat manipulation versus no intervention**

65 It is uncertain whether the use of floodgates reduces malaria incidence or parasite prevalence compared
66 to no intervention because the certainty of the evidence are very low. However, floodgates on a dam may
67 reduce the density of immature mosquitoes compared to no intervention (low certainty of evidence).

68 It is uncertain whether the use of spillways across streams reduces malaria parasite prevalence compared
69 to no intervention because the certainty of evidence is very low (very low certainty of evidence); however,
70 spillways probably reduce the density of immature and adult mosquitoes (moderate certainty of
71 evidence).

72 The density of immature mosquitoes is probably reduced with increasingly faster drawdown rates of
73 water compared to no drawdown of water (moderate certainty of evidence).

74 Using intermittent irrigation of rice fields results probably results in a greater absolute density of
75 immature mosquitoes compared to continuously flooding (moderate certainty of evidence).

76 Shading of using Napier grass reduces densities of immature mosquitoes compared to no intervention
77 (high certainty of evidence). Shading using unweeded rice habitats, or providing coverage using arrow
78 root or water ferns may reduce density of immature mosquitoes compared to no intervention (low
79 certainty of evidence).

80 Frequent and intermediate disturbance of habitats through clearing grass and replenishing water from
81 local streams increases the density of immature mosquitoes compared to no intervention (high certainty
82 of evidence).

83

84 **Comparison 2. Habitat manipulation with larviciding versus no intervention**

85 Repairing and clearing of drains, cutting grasses and making minor repairs (e.g. slab replacement)
86 combined with larviciding may reduce malaria parasite prevalence compared to no intervention (low
87 certainty of evidence).

88

89 **Comparison 3. Combination of habitat manipulation and modification versus no intervention**

90 Construction of drainage canals, planting of papyrus and other reeds for shading near dams probably
91 reduces the density of adult mosquitoes compared to no intervention (moderate certainty of evidence).

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92 Preventing water stagnating using drainage of canals, removal of debris, land levelling, and filling ditches
93 with soil reduces the density of immature mosquitoes compared to no intervention (high certainty of
94 evidence).

95

96 ***Comparison 4. Habitat manipulation and modification with larviciding versus no intervention***

97 Filling, drainage, or elimination of rain pools and puddles at water supply points and stream pools bedded
98 with sediment probably reduces the density of immature and adult mosquitoes when delivered with
99 larviciding compared to no intervention (moderate certainty of evidence).

100

101 **Author's conclusion:**

102 In Africa and Asia, habitat modification and manipulation interventions could be considered as part of an
103 integrated approach to control malaria in rural and urban areas, however, the certainty of evidence varies
104 greatly depending on the technique employed. As techniques explored were largely dependent on the
105 site of the study, caution is needed in interpreting and extrapolating results to other ecological areas. Very
106 few studies used epidemiological data to assess the effectiveness of interventions and for each study
107 which did report epidemiological outcomes, the certainty of evidence was low or very low. Therefore,
108 without epidemiological evidence or sufficient robust studies demonstrating that a significant reduction
109 in immature/adult mosquito vector densities translates directly into reduced incidence of disease, it is
110 difficult to recommend habitat manipulation/modification for controlling malaria incidence or parasite
111 prevalence based on the evidence reviewed.

112

113 In specific sites, this review supports the effectiveness of shading of drainage canals using Napier grass as
114 a habitat manipulation strategy; and preventing water stagnating using drainage of canals, removal of
115 debris, land levelling, and filling ditches with soil as a combination of habitat manipulation and
116 modification strategy, for reducing the density of immature mosquitoes, compared to no intervention.
117 Although it is acknowledged that there is a wealth of historical research on the environmental
118 management of malaria, unfortunately this literature was insufficiently robust to be included in this
119 systematic review. Therefore, further well-designed studies, using controlled before-after or randomised
120 controlled design, are needed to evaluate the effectiveness of such interventions, particularly in relation
121 to epidemiological outcomes relating to malaria. However, in the absence of such studies, national
122 programmes may decide to use habitat manipulation and/or modification interventions to avoid the

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123 creation, and reduce the availability of larval habitats, where deemed appropriate, based on expert
124 guidance and local knowledge.

125 **BACKGROUND**

126 **Description of the condition**

127 Malaria is an important public health priority, which is caused by *Plasmodium* parasites and is transmitted
128 to humans by adult female mosquitoes of the genus *Anopheles*. Between 2010 and 2017, the estimated
129 number of deaths due to malaria declined globally from 607,000 to 435,000 cases. A total of 266,000
130 (61%) malaria deaths were estimated to be in children under five in 2017, and the World Health
131 Organization (WHO) African Region accounted for the 93% (1-3).

132 **Description of the intervention**

133 For the prevention of malaria, in 2019, the WHO published guidelines which provide recommendations
134 on vector control strategies (2). Long-lasting insecticide treated bed nets (LLINs) and indoor residual
135 spraying (IRS) are the core interventions to reduce malaria transmission by targeting the adult mosquito
136 population. Larval source management (LSM) is an additional method for malaria control targeting
137 immature forms of mosquitoes (larvae and pupae), which thrive in aquatic habitats. There are four types
138 of LSM: i) larviciding: the regular application of biological or chemical insecticides to water bodies, ii)
139 biological control: the introduction of natural predators into water, iii) habitat modification: a permanent
140 alteration to the environment, e.g. land reclamation and filling; and iv) habitat manipulation: a recurrent
141 activity, e.g. flushing of streams and drain clearance(3, 4). These LSM activities are made with the express
142 purpose of controlling larvae, particularly where a permanent alteration to the environment is made using
143 habitat modification activities. However, habitat modification and habitat manipulation activities can also
144 be used for other purposes, such as for irrigation for agriculture or power generation, which may also
145 have an effect on immature forms of mosquitoes.

146
147 The effectiveness of both larviciding and larvivorous fish (biological control) was recently systematically
148 reviewed by the Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group (5, 6). For the use of larviciding, it was concluded
149 that this intervention is conditionally recommended for use in specific areas and in particular
150 circumstances as a supplementary measure alongside the core interventions (5). With regards to
151 biological control with larvivorous fish, the evidence was not sufficient to make a recommendation (6).
152 Habitat manipulation and modification was systematically reviewed in 2005 (7) and 2013 (8). The
153 conclusions of the reviews were that very high protective effects on clinical malaria were seen irrespective
154 of the type of habitat modification and/or manipulation strategy used (7) and LSM is a policy option which
155 can be used alongside LLINs and IRS for reducing malaria morbidity where a sufficient proportion of larval

156 habitats can be targeted (8); but no recommendations were included in the last WHO Guidelines for
157 Vector control (2).

158 **How the intervention might work**

159

160

HABITAT MODIFICATION (permanent alteration to the environment)

161

&

162

HABITAT MANIPULATION (any recurrent activity to the environment)

163

164

165

MAIN EFFECTS

166

- Reduced larval mosquito density
- Reduced adult mosquito density
- Reduced entomological inoculation rate (EIR)
- Sporozoite rate in adult mosquitoes

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168

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IMPACTS

172

- Reduced clinical malaria incidence
- Reduced severe malaria incidence
- Reduced malaria parasitaemia incidence
- Reduced malaria parasite prevalence
- Reduced mortality due to malaria
- Reduced anemia prevalence
- Increased mean haemoglobin levels (g/dl)
- Reduced hospital admissions for malaria

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179 *Figure 1.* Logic model that describes the effects of habitat modification and habitat manipulation
180 interventions.

181 Implementing LSM interventions, which target habitats of immature stages of the *Anopheles* vectors,
182 could potentially reduce the number of adult mosquitoes and parasite transmission (9). A logic model
183 (Figure 1) describes the main epidemiological and entomological outcomes of habitat modification and
184 habitat manipulation interventions.

185 **Why it is important to do this review**

186 An updated systematic review is required now to determine whether there is sufficient evidence available
187 to inform the development of policy recommendations for larval habitat modification and/or
188 manipulation for controlling malaria, so as to ensure that the evolving World Health Organization (WHO)
189 guidelines for malaria vector control are based on the most up-to-date information.

190 **Objectives**

- 191 1. To describe and summarise the interventions on larval habitat modification and larval habitat
192 manipulation
- 193 2. To evaluate the beneficial and environmental impacts of larval habitat modification and larval
194 habitat manipulation on malaria

195

196 **METHODS**

197

198 **Criteria for considering studies for this review**

199 **Types of studies**

200 We included the following study designs for the evaluation of the effectiveness of the interventions:

- 201 • Randomised trials (parallel and cluster designs)
- 202 • Randomised cross-over trials
- 203 • Stepped wedge cluster randomised trials (SW-CRT)
- 204 • Non-randomised intervention studies, including but not limited to, controlled before-after (CBA)
205 studies and interrupted time series (ITS) studies

206 We included cluster randomised trials (cRCT) which have at least two intervention and two comparator
207 sites, and CBA studies which have at least two intervention and two comparator sites. Where insufficient
208 cRCT or CBA studies were identified for each type of interventions, we relaxed the number of sites

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209 restriction. We included ITS studies which have at least three data points before and three data points
210 after the intervention, and where there was a clearly defined point in time when the intervention
211 occurred.

212 We also included the following lower form of evidence in addition to those detailed above for describing
213 and summarizing all types of eligible interventions:

- 214 • Uncontrolled before-after (BA) studies

215 We will include studies irrespective of their publication status and language of publication.

216 **Types of participants**

217 We included all participants, irrespective of age, gender, and ethnicity, residing in countries/regions with
218 any level of malaria endemicity.

219 **Types of interventions**

220 Eligible interventions included any that aim to either modify or manipulate the habitat of the aquatic
221 stages of *Anopheles* so as to reduce or completely avoid its presence.

222 *Habitat modification*

223 This included any permanent alteration to the environment such as land reclamation and filling,
224 landscaping, drainage of surface water, coverage of large water storage containers (e.g. wells) with
225 mosquito-proof lids and permanent slabs or complete coverage of water surfaces with a material that is
226 impenetrable to mosquitoes (e.g. expanded polystyrene beads).

227 *Habitat manipulation*

228 This included any recurrent activity to the environment such as flushing of streams, water level
229 manipulation, drain clearance, shading or exposing habitats to the sun.

230

231 Habitat modification or manipulation may be used alone or in combination with other interventions,
232 including biological control of anopheline mosquitoes or larvicidal treatments. Where habitat
233 modification or manipulation was combined with other core malaria interventions (such as insecticide-
234 treated nets (ITNs) or indoor residual spraying (IRS)), studies were only included where the same
235 additional core intervention was given to both the intervention and control groups. Regarding other LSM
236 interventions, we included studies which evaluated larval habitat modification or manipulation in
237 combination with biological control of anopheline mosquitoes or larvicidal treatments when compared to
238 the use of the biological control or larvicidal or to no intervention. In this last case, we have noted where

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239 it would not be appropriate to report the results of the study because the effect of the eligible intervention
240 cannot be distinguished from the effect of the core malaria intervention.

241

242 **Types of outcome measures**

243 *Primary outcomes*

244 Epidemiological

- 245 • Clinical malaria incidence

246 Defined as new malaria cases during a defined period in a specific population demonstrating the presence
247 of malaria parasites by blood smear or a rapid diagnostic test (RDT), or both; and clinical symptoms
248 including fever or history of fever, detected passively or actively.

- 249 • Malaria parasite prevalence

250 Defined as the proportion of the human population with malaria parasites circulating in the blood
251 (diagnostically confirmed by RDT or microscopy)

- 252 • Malaria parasitaemia incidence

253 Defined as new malaria infections, with parasitaemia diagnostically confirmed by RDT or microscopy.

254 *Secondary outcomes*

255 Epidemiological

- 256 • Incidence of severe malaria, characterised by (a) and either (b) or (c) (10)

257 (a) demonstration of parasitaemia by blood smear

258 (b) symptoms of cerebral malaria including coma or prostration or multiple seizures

259 (c) severe life-threatening anaemia

- 260 • Anaemia prevalence (11)

- 261 • Mean haemoglobin levels (g/dl)

- 262 • Mortality rate due to malaria

- 263 • Hospital admissions for malaria

264 Entomological

- 265 1. Density of immature mosquitoes.

266 Immature mosquitoes collected with a standard dipping method.

- 267 • Density of adult mosquitoes measured by:

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- 268 ○ Human biting rate: number of mosquitoes per person per time period, measured directly
269 using human baits, or indirectly using light traps, baited huts, or other methods of biting
270 rate determination.
- 271 ○ Other density measures: number of mosquitoes per person or catch, measured using light
272 traps, knock-down catches, baited huts, or other methods of adult vector density
273 determination.
- 274 • Sporozoite rate: defined as the number of caught adult mosquitoes positive for malaria
275 sporozoites in their salivary glands observed by dissection or detected by molecular or
276 immunological methods.
- 277 • Entomological inoculation rate (EIR): the estimated number of bites by infectious mosquitoes per
278 person per unit time (measured directly using human baits or indirectly using CDC light traps, ,
279 baited huts, human-landing catch and infectivity determined as defined under the ‘sporozoite
280 rate’ listed above).

281 Harms defined as adverse events related to the intervention

282

283 Search methods for identification of studies

284 Electronic searches

285 Relevant studies were identified through comprehensive electronic searches using the following
286 databases, from January 2012 (previous search date was up to 24th October 2012; (8)) to
287 September/October 2019:

- 288 • Cochrane Infectious Diseases Group Specialized Register (CIDG SR) (11th October 2019)
289 • Cochrane Central Register of Controlled Trials (CENTRAL) (24th September 2019)
290 • MEDLINE (2nd October 2019)
291 • Embase (2nd October 2019)
292 • CAB Abstracts (2nd October 2019)
293 • LILACS (20th September 2019)

294

295 Using search terms from the previous Cochrane review (8) as initial terms, we further developed the
296 search strategies for each database using comprehensive search terms for the intervention and outcomes.

297 The full search strategy for each database is reported in the Supplementary Table 1.

298 Searching other resources

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299 Additionally, further studies were identified through other relevant databases and hand searching of grey
300 literature sources:

- 301 • Global Health
- 302 • ProQuest Natural Science Collection
- 303 • ZETOC
- 304 • Tropical Diseases Bulletin
- 305 • The Archives of the World Health Organization
- 306 • The Literature Database of the Armed Forces Pest Management Board
- 307 • US National Institute of Health Ongoing Trials Register (www.ClinicalTrials.gov/)
- 308 • ISRCTN registry (www.isrctn.com/)
- 309 • The WHO's International Clinical Trials Registry Platform (WHO ICTRP) (www.who.int.ictcp)

310 Where required, experts within the field of habitat modification and manipulation as vector control
311 methods for malaria were contacted to provide information about ongoing and further completed
312 studies. Forward and backwards citation tracking was conducted of all studies screened at the full text
313 screening stage. The reference lists of included studies were screened to identify any further eligible
314 studies. No language restrictions were applied, and translations were sought where necessary. In cases of
315 dual publication of a study, the most informative study publication was used.

316 We also scanned the list of studies excluded at the full text stage from the previous Cochrane review (8);
317 which allowed us to reconsider any relevant studies, which met our amended inclusion criteria.

318

319 **Data collection and analysis**

320 **Selection of studies**

321 All hits identified from the searches were imported into a bibliographic database, Mendeley Desktop
322 (London, UK). Following de-duplication of the hits, two reviewers independently screened titles and
323 abstracts according to the inclusion/exclusion criteria and an inter-rater agreement measure was
324 calculated. Full-text papers were sought for all studies, which were included at the title and abstract stage.
325 Where insufficient information was available in the title and abstract, the full text of the article was
326 retrieved for further inspection. Two reviewers independently screened the full-text papers, and an inter-
327 rater agreement measure was calculated. Any disagreements were resolved by consensus or by a third
328 reviewer. Studies excluded at the full text stage were reported together with the reason for exclusion.

329 **Data extraction and management**

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330 Two reviewers independently extracted data using a previously piloted data extraction form within a
331 spreadsheet database. Initially the data extraction form was piloted independently by two reviewers on
332 a random sample of three included studies to enable an assessment of consistency in data extraction and
333 to identify where amendments needed to be made to the template. Any disagreements were discussed
334 or, if necessary, resolved by a third reviewer.

335 Assessment of risk of bias in included studies

336 Two reviewers independently assessed the risk of bias of the results for each outcome measure of the
337 included studies using an assessment of risk of bias tool appropriate to the design of the study. The
338 Cochrane Risk of Bias 2.0 tool (12) was used for randomised controlled trials and cluster randomised
339 controlled trials (with signalling questions relating to the following domains: for randomisation process,
340 timing of identification and recruitment of individual participants in relation to timing of randomization
341 [cluster trials only], deviations from the intended interventions, missing outcome data, measurement of
342 the outcome, and selection of the reported result), with judgements reported as low, some concerns, or
343 high. For non-randomised controlled studies, the ROBINS-I risk of bias assessment (13) (within domains
344 for confounding, selection of participants, classification of interventions, deviations from intended
345 interventions, missing data, measurement of outcomes, and selection of reported results), was used, with
346 judgements reported as low, moderate, serious, or critical. A comparison between the findings from the
347 Cochrane Risk of Bias 2.0 and the ROBINS-I tool cannot be performed due to important differences
348 between the domains considered in the tools. Uncontrolled before-and-after studies were assigned a
349 critical overall risk of bias due to the inherent biases associated with the study design. Any disagreements
350 were discussed, or where necessary, resolved by a third reviewer.

351 Measures of treatment effect

352 The results from studies with eligible designs for assessing the effectiveness of the interventions were
353 extracted as either adjusted effect measures, crude effect measures or as raw data. Where possible, we
354 have reported dichotomous outcomes using risk ratios, count data using rate ratios, and continuous data
355 using mean difference based on either arithmetic or geometric means, together with 95% confidence
356 intervals (CI). P values from statistical testing were extracted as reported in the publications for eligible
357 designs of studies which did not present quantitative results.

358 Unit of analysis issues

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359 For cluster-randomised trials, which did not account for clustering in their analyses, we attempted to
360 contact authors of the trials to provide estimates of the interclass correlation coefficient (ICC).

361 Dealing with missing data

362 Where possible, we contacted the authors of the included studies with eligible designs for assessing the
363 effectiveness of interventions to provide missing data relating to results, for example, measures of
364 dispersion.

365 Assessment of heterogeneity

366 Due to insufficient studies for each intervention, we were unable to quantify heterogeneity between the
367 studies using I^2 (Higgins 2003). We would have considered a value greater than 50% to reflect substantial
368 heterogeneity between findings of RCTs. However, due to the inherent biases within other experimental
369 designs, we would have considered a value greater than 75% to reflect substantial heterogeneity for these
370 studies.

371 Assessment of reporting biases

372 Due to insufficient studies for each intervention (<10 studies), we were unable to assess evidence of
373 publication bias (small-study bias) using funnel plots.

374 Data synthesis

375 For all study designs, except uncontrolled before-and-after studies, we initially used a narrative synthesis
376 approach to systematically describe and summarise all the interventions considered in the studies fulfilling
377 the inclusion criteria. The studies were categorised by the type of intervention (habitat modification alone,
378 habitat manipulation alone, combination of habitat modification and manipulation), and the type of
379 manipulation /modification, for example water management, and the purpose of the intervention (LSM,
380 non-LSM).

381

382 Where possible, the quantitative findings from all included studies, except those which used an
383 uncontrolled before-after design, were analysed to assess the effectiveness of the interventions. Due to
384 insufficient studies, we were not able to conduct random effects meta-analysis models to pool data from
385 studies to estimate a weighted treatment effect for each categorisation of the type of intervention. A
386 random effects model was deemed most appropriate due to the anticipated differences in protocols and
387 inherent biases within the study designs, which are likely to impact the magnitude of the effectiveness of

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388 the interventions. Findings from meta-analyses would have been reported using appropriate measures of
389 effect together with 95% confidence intervals.

390

391 For uncontrolled before/after studies, we categorised these studies based on the definition and type of
392 the intervention (manipulation or modification or combination) and the purpose of the intervention (LSM,
393 non-LSM). We then provided comprehensive narrative descriptions of each study including the nature
394 and scope of the considered interventions and the outcomes assessed. Results from the studies were
395 reported in terms of the clinical significance of the effect, but no statistical inferences were made.

396

397 **Assessment of certainty of evidence**

398 Two reviewers were involved in the process of assessing the certainty of the evidence for each
399 intervention across each critical or important outcome measure using the Grading of Recommendations,
400 Assessment, Development and Evaluation (GRADE) method (14). Critical outcome measures were: clinical
401 malaria incidence, malaria parasite prevalence, and incidence of severe malaria. Important outcome
402 measures were: malaria parasitaemia incidence, mortality rate due to malaria, and density of immature
403 mosquitoes. Randomised and non-randomised intervention studies were initially ranked as high. The
404 certainty of evidence was downgraded if there was evidence of the following 1) risk of bias, 2) imprecision,
405 3) inconsistency of evidence, 4) indirectness, and 5) publication bias. The first four domains were rated as
406 either 'very serious', 'serious' or 'not serious' and were downgraded by one where a 'serious' rating was
407 given or by two where a 'very serious' rating was given; no downgrading was applied for those rated as
408 'not serious'. The risk of bias domain was rated as 'serious' where the overall risk of bias was classified as
409 high for RCT designed studies or serious for one domain for non-randomised intervention designed studies
410 and a 'very serious' where the overall risk of bias was serious in more than one domain for non-
411 randomised intervention design studies. The imprecision domain was rated as 'serious' where small event
412 rates (<400) or wide confidence intervals were reported and 'very serious' where the number of events
413 were very small (<100). The inconsistency domain was rated as 'serious' where there was evidence of
414 inconsistency in the findings of multiple studies; the indirectness domain was rated as 'serious' where
415 there was evidence of indirectness of the population, intervention, or outcome measure and 'very serious'
416 where there was evidence of indirectness in at least two of population, intervention or outcome measure.
417 The final domain (publication bias) was rated as either suspected or not suspected; a rating of 'suspected'
418 was given if there was evidence of publication bias from a funnel plot. Due to only intervention studies

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419 being considered, upgrading of the certainty of evidence was not considered. The final certainty of
420 evidence was interpreted as follows:

421

Certainty	Interpretation
Very Low	The true effect is markedly different from the estimated effect
Low	The true effect might be markedly different from the estimated effect
Moderate	The authors believe that the true effect is probably close to the estimated effect
High	The authors have a lot of confidence that the true effect is similar to the estimated effect

422 **Subgroup analysis and investigation of heterogeneity**

423 Where data permitted, we planned to investigate sources of heterogeneity in the meta-analyses using
424 subgroup analyses based on:

- 425 • Different eco-epidemiological settings, for example: malaria of deep forests, forest fringe, and
426 hills; rural malaria attributable to irrigation and large dams; rural malaria attributable to wetlands,
427 rivers, streams, coasts, and non-agricultural man-made water habitats; and urban and peri-urban
428 malaria ((7));
- 429 • Participants (< 5 years, pregnant woman, adult, mixed age groups);
- 430 • Species of the main vector/s
- 431 • WHO region

432 **Sensitivity analysis**

433 Where data permitted, we planned to perform sensitivity analyses to assess the effect of study design on
434 the primary and secondary outcomes using stratification. We also planned to assess the effect of excluding
435 studies with serious/critical risk of bias in at least one domain of the risk of bias assessment.

436

437 **Pre-specified changes for review update**

438 A table (Supplementary Table 2) with the main differences in performing this review update compared
439 with the previous one (8) was provided.

440

441

442 **RESULTS**

443 **Description of studies**

444 We have provided descriptions of the included and excluded studies in the Characteristics of included
445 studies (Appendix 1), Supplementary table 3 and Characteristics of excluded studies (Appendix 2).

446

447 **Results of the search**

448 In this review, we identified 3317 studies through database searching. After duplicates had been removed,
449 a total of 2182 records were screened by title and abstract. Then, we excluded 2149 records and included
450 33 to assess full text for eligibility. A total of 15 full-text articles were included while 18 were excluded.
451 One included study has no data available yet and is therefore reported within the Ongoing Studies section.
452 In the previous version of this Cochrane Review(8) 13 studies were identified as meeting their inclusion
453 criteria, but, only six studies were evaluating the interventions included in this specific review update.
454 Only five of the six studies were included in this updated review. One study was excluded as the habitat
455 modification intervention was so poorly described that it was not clear when the constructing of the
456 intervention started or whether it was complete by the end of the study (15). The two additional
457 interventions included in the previous review (use of larvivorous fish or larviciding with no habitat
458 modification or manipulation) were recently reviewed (5, 6) and excluded from this update. The PRISMA
459 study flow diagram, illustrates the study selection process (Figure 2,(16)).

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460

461

Figure 2. PRISMA flow chart

462 **Included studies**

463 The characteristics of the 14 included studies are presented in the Characteristics of included studies table
464 (Appendix 1). The one ongoing included study is presented in the 'Ongoing studies' section and not
465 included in the text below describing the included studies.

466 **Design**

467 Of the 14 included studies, one used a parallel randomised controlled trial design (17), four used a cluster-
468 randomised controlled trial design (18-21), six used a controlled before-after study design (22-27), two
469 used non-randomised controlled trials (28, 29), and the remaining study used an uncontrolled before-
470 after study design (30).

471 **Location**

472 Most of the studies (9) were conducted in Africa (Kenya, Eritrea, Tanzania, or Ethiopia) (17-21, 25, 26, 28,
473 29) and five studies in Asia (Philippines, India, Japan, Sri Lanka) (22-24, 27, 30).

474 **Purpose and types of interventions**

475 The purpose of the intervention was LSM in all except for one of the included studies, where the purpose
476 was irrigation (23). The types of interventions were classified into four comparisons based on i) habitat
477 manipulation (sub-category: a) water management approaches [5 studies], b) shading management
478 approaches [3 studies], c) other/combined approaches [1 study]); ii) habitat manipulation with larviciding
479 (2 studies); iii) combination of habitat manipulation and modification (2 studies); iv) combination of
480 habitat manipulation and modification with larviciding (2 studies). The total adds up to more than the
481 included number of studies because one study reported two different interventions (28). The specific
482 interventions are described below for each study.

483

484 **1. Habitat manipulation versus no intervention**

485 A total of nine of the included studies assessed the effects of habitat manipulation versus no intervention.
486 (17, 19-23, 27-29) The habitat manipulation interventions took either a water management approach,
487 shading management approach or another/combined management approach.

488 **a. Water management approaches:**

489 Five studies compared the effect of water management as a habitat manipulation approach versus no
490 intervention. (19, 21-23, 27) The specific interventions considered were:

- 491
- 492 • Different drawn down rates of water versus no drawn down in ground pools (21)
 - 493 • Different flooding and draining regimens versus continuously flooding of irrigated rice fields (19)
 - Spillways (automatic siphons) versus no spillway across streams (22)

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- 494 • Floodgates (sluice gates) versus no flood gates on a bed dam (27)
- 495 • Floodgates (sluice gates) versus no flood gates on a dam [non-LSM purpose] (23)

496

497 ***b. Shading management approaches:***

498 Three studies compared the effect of shading management as a habitat manipulation approach versus no
499 intervention. (17, 28, 29) The specific interventions considered were:

- 500 • Shading with a range of crop and non-crop plants versus no shading (29)
- 501 • Shading with arrowroot versus no shading (28)
- 502 • Shading with Napier grass versus no shading (17)

503

504 ***c. Other/combined management approaches:***

505 One study compared the effect of other/combinatiion management as a habitat manipulation approach
506 versus no intervention. (20) The specific intervention considered was:

- 507 • Disturbance of larval habitat with grass clearing and water replenishment versus no disturbance
508 (20)

509

510 **2. Habitat manipulation with larviciding versus no intervention**

511 A total of two of the included studies assessed the effects of habitat manipulation with larviciding versus
512 no intervention. (24, 25) The specific interventions considered were:

- 513 • Reduce or removal of domestic larval habits sites with larviciding versus no intervention (24)
- 514 • Drain cleaning, grass cutting and minor repairs (e.g. slab replacement) with larviciding versus no
515 intervention (25)

516

517 **3. Combination of habitat manipulation and modification versus no intervention**

518 Two of the included studies assessed the combined effects of habitat manipulation and modification
519 versus no intervention. (26, 28) The specific intervention considered was:

- 520 • Construction of drainage canals, prohibition and filling of crossing points of cattle and humans
521 along riverbed, draining the base of dam embankment, and shading using papyrus and other
522 reeds versus no intervention (26)
- 523 • Drainage of canals, land levelling or filling ditches with soil versus no intervention (28)

524

525 **4. Combination of habitat manipulation and modification with larviciding versus no intervention**

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526 Two of the included studies assessed the combined effect of habitat manipulation and modification with
527 larviciding versus no intervention. (18, 30) The specific interventions considered were:

- 528 • Filling or drainage or elimination of rain pools, puddles at water supply points and stream bed
529 pools with larviciding versus no intervention (18)
- 530 • Shoreline work, improvement to drainage, maintenance of drains, clearing of vegetation and
531 undergrowth, filling up pools of water, with larviciding (note: uncontrolled study, thus no
532 comparator group) (30)

533

534 Larviciding

535 A total of four studies combined the active intervention with larviciding (18, 24, 25, 30). The larviciding
536 used in the four studies were either *Bacillus thuringiensis israelensis* (Bti) alone (30), pirimiphos-methyl
537 alone (24), or Bti, *Bacillus sphaericus* (Bsp) and Temephos larvicide in rotation (18), with the fourth study
538 not specifying (25).

539

540 Co-interventions

541 A range of different co-interventions were described within the included studies. These included case
542 management and treatment for fever cases (24), IRS with DDT (25, 26), the Roll Back Malaria initiative,
543 which comprised of ITNs, IRS, and anti-malarial drugs (28) or routine malaria control activities under the
544 primary health care system included indoor residual spraying with DDT (22). Two studies provided no
545 information about co-interventions (17, (22), and a further study was unclear but possibly used IRS with
546 DDT (27). The remaining six studies reported no co-interventions; however, for one of these studies ITNs
547 and IRS were conducted as part of the national malaria control program (coverage not stated) (18).

548

549 Outcomes

550 Only one study reported the incidence of clinical malaria, which was in participants in all ages (23). Four
551 studies measured the primary outcome malaria parasite prevalence, with studies reporting the outcome
552 in either children aged 2-10 years and infants (22), children under the age of 10 years (26), or in
553 participants of all ages (23, 25). None of the included studies reported secondary epidemiological
554 outcomes of incidence of severe malaria, anaemia prevalence, mean haemoglobin levels, mortality due
555 to malaria, or hospital admissions for malaria. Secondary entomological outcomes were reported in the
556 majority of the included studies.

557

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558 The density of immature mosquitoes was evaluated in 13 studies, with 11 studies reporting as larvae (17-
559 19, 21, 22, 24, 26, 28, 29, 31), two studies as larvae plus pupae (20, 25), and one study as larvae and/or
560 pupae (27). The density of adult mosquitoes was reported in five studies (18, 22, 24, 26, 30). One study
561 reported the entomological inoculation rate (EIR)(22). None of the included studies reported on other
562 outcomes of the environmental impacts associated with the intervention.

563

564 **Vectors and eco-epidemiology of study areas**

565 The nine included studies which were performed in Africa (17-21, 25, 26, 28, 29) had the following primary
566 vectors: *Anopheles gambiae* and *An. arabiensis*. Other *Anopheles* spp. collected within these studies
567 included: *An. funestus*, *An. coustani*, *An. cinereus*, *An. rufipes*, *An. marshalli*, *An. maculipalpis*, *An. azaniae*,
568 *An. implexus*, *An. pretoriensis*, *An. d'thali*, *An. squamosus*, *An. adenensis*, *An. demeilloni* and *An.*
569 *pharoensis*. In the five included studies which were performed in Asia (22-24, 27, 30), the most common
570 vectors were: *An. minimus flavirostris*, *An. fluviatilis*, *An. culicifacies*, *An. stephensi*, *An. sondaicus*, *An.*
571 *maculates*, *An. maculipennis*, *An. vagus*, *An. annularis*, and *An. subpictus*. The majority of studies which
572 reported entomological outcomes did not analyze the data by *Anopheles* species.

573

574 Most of the studies were performed in rural areas (17-21, 23, 26-28, 30) with other studies conducted in
575 solely urban areas (24, 25), solely semi-urban areas (29), or a combination of urban and semi-urban areas
576 (22).

577

578 **Responsibility of the delivery of the intervention**

579 The interventions within the included studies were coordinated and performed by different people and/or
580 institutions. The study staff and the local community were involved in the intervention activities in four
581 studies (18, 24-26). In four studies the institutions responsible for the delivery of the interventions were
582 either the Armed Forces (30), an irrigation and agricultural development experimental station (19), or the
583 District Rural Development Agency (DRDA) (23, 27). The remaining five studies did not clearly report who
584 delivered the interventions (17, 20, 21, 28, 29).

585

586 **Ongoing studies**

587 One ongoing study was included in the review (31). The study used a 2x2 factorial, cluster-randomised
588 controlled trial design to evaluate habitat modification, as part of an integrated vector control
589 intervention, on the impact on malaria transmission and burden over a two year study intervention

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590 period, in 53 villages within a rural area in Southern Malawi. The trial assesses the effectiveness of habitat
591 modification of either draining or filling water bodies, with or without house improvements. All
592 intervention groups received the use of larviciding (using Bti). Housing improvements included material
593 modification to block entry of malaria vectors, such as closing eaves, closing all holes in the wall not used
594 for ventilation or modifying doors to cover doorways when closed. Community members were
595 encouraged to actively participate to the interventions and professional training and workshops were
596 made available to them. Eligible outcome measures included: malaria parasite prevalence in children 6-
597 59 months; clinical malaria incidence in in children 6-59 months; anaemia prevalence in children 6-59
598 months; entomological inoculation rate (EIR); density of immature mosquitoes; and the density of adult
599 mosquitoes.

600

601 **Excluded studies**

602 We excluded 18 studies after full-text screening for the following reasons as detailed in the Characteristics
603 of excluded studies (Appendix 2):

- 604 • Study design did not match inclusion criteria (n=5) and specifically they were: review paper (32),
605 modelling paper (33), cross-sectional study (34), observational study (35, 36)
- 606 • Intervention did not match inclusion criteria (n=11) and specifically: abstracts from Symposium with
607 wrong or no intervention in place (37-41), no intervention described (42-46), ineligible intervention
608 described (47)
- 609 • Intervention was too poorly reported to determine when it was initiated and whether the design was
610 observational in nature (15)
- 611 • Duplicate record (48) of an ongoing study (31)

612

613 **Risk of bias in included studies**

614 The summary Risk of Bias assessment of the included studies is shown in Appendix 1.

615

616 For the RCTs, the risk of bias was assessed using either the standard or cluster-RCT extension to the
617 Cochrane Risk of Bias 2.0 tool (17-21). All of the RCTs reported the secondary outcome, density of
618 immature mosquitoes; and one RCT also reported the density of adult mosquitoes. (18) The overall risk
619 of bias was 'high' for one cluster-RCT (19) and of 'some concerns' for the remaining three cluster-RCTs
620 and individual RCT (Figures 3 and 4).

621 ***Randomization process***

622 Some concerns in relation to the bias arising from the randomization process were identified in all five
623 studies (17-21). Although all five studies reported that the interventions were 'randomly' allocated, the
624 methods for generating the randomisation sequence were missing from four RCTs (17, 18, 20, 21). The
625 fifth RCT reported that the randomisation sequence was performed using block sizes of 4 (19). Some
626 concerns regarding allocation concealment were identified in all five RCTs due to none of the studies
627 reporting whether the randomisation sequence was blinded (allocation concealment) (17-21).

628 ***Timing of identification and recruitment of individuals in relation to timing of randomization***
629 ***(cluster-RCTs only)***

630 For the four cluster-RCTs, the bias arising from the timing of identification and recruitment of individuals
631 in relation to timing of randomization was deemed to be a low risk of bias. (18-21)

632 ***Deviations from the intended interventions***

633 Although the trial personnel were aware of the assigned interventions during the trial, because there were
634 no deviations from the intended intervention and no clusters or individuals were analysed in a different
635 group to the one which they were randomized, then four of the studies were deemed to have a low risk
636 of bias for this domain (17, 18, 20, 21). However, for one trial, a high risk of bias was noted as there was
637 evidence of contamination of intervention where seepage occurred from continuously flooded to
638 adjacent subplots, thereby resulting in an unbalance between groups and likely to have affected the
639 outcome. (19)

640 ***Missing outcome data***

641 For the outcome, density of immature mosquitoes, a low risk of bias was found within all of the RCTs since
642 data were available for all, or nearly all, of individuals randomized (17-21) and for all clusters randomized.
643 (18-21) A low risk of bias was given for the individual study which reported density of adult mosquitoes,
644 for the same reason. (18)

645 ***Measurement of the outcome***

646 For the outcome, density of immature mosquitoes, although the outcome assessors were aware of the
647 intervention received by the individuals, the assessment of the outcome was unlikely to be influenced by
648 this knowledge of the intervention received due to it being an objective measures which was assessed
649 using standard methods; therefore, a low risk of bias was found within all of the RCTs (17-21). A low risk
650 of bias for the measurement of the outcome was also given for the outcome measure density of adult
651 mosquitoes, for the same reason. (18)

652 ***Selection of the reported results***

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653 For the outcome, density of immature mosquitoes, four of the cluster-RCTs were deemed to have a low
 654 risk of bias due to the reported outcome data being unlikely to be selected on the basis of the results (18-
 655 21), although one cluster-RCT reported multiple results based on or wet and dry seasons (21); the results
 656 were similar therefore not suggesting any selection. The RCT (17) was deemed to have some concerns risk
 657 of bias due to no pre-specified analysis plan; although the RCT reported multiple results based on
 658 stratifying by village; the results were similar therefore not suggesting any selection.
 659

660
 661 *Figure 3.* Risk of Bias traffic light plot of included studies with cluster-RCT designs for secondary outcome,
 662 density of immature mosquitoes (RoB)
 663

664

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665 *Figure 4.* Risk of Bias traffic light plot of included studies with RCT design for secondary outcome, density
666 of immature mosquitoes (RoB)

667

668 Eight of the included studies were assessed for risk of bias using the ROBINS-I tool (22-29) for the primary
669 outcomes, clinical malaria incidence and malaria parasite prevalence; and for the secondary outcome,
670 density of immature mosquitoes, density of adult mosquitoes and entomological inoculation rate (EIR).

671

672 For one study (24), an overall critical risk of bias was given for all outcomes assessed due to critical
673 concerns regarding bias due to confounding and bias due to deviations from the intervention. The study
674 was deemed too problematic to provide any useful evidence; therefore, the findings from this study are
675 not reported in the results; however, a full description of the intervention conducted in the study is
676 presented. (24)

677

678 In the remaining seven studies, the overall risk of bias by each outcome measure was (Figures 5-9):

679

- Clinical malaria incidence – Serious in one study (23)
- Malaria parasite prevalence – Serious in two studies (22, 23) and moderate in one study (25)
- Density of immature mosquitoes – Serious in four studies (22, 26, 27, 29) and moderate in one study (28)
- Density of adult mosquitoes – Serious in two studies (22, 26)

684

685 ***Confounding***

686 Only one study had a low risk of bias where it was very unlikely that confounding would exist between the
687 intervention groups due to the intervention and control being conducted within the same village with the
688 same timings and the analysis accounting for changes from baseline (28). One study had a moderate risk
689 of bias due to the analysis taking into account confounding of several important factors (25). However,
690 the remaining five studies had a serious risk of bias due to the differences at baseline in the outcome
691 measure and no adjustment for important confounders (22, 23, 26, 27, 29).

692

693 ***Selection of participants***

694 All seven studies had a low risk of selection bias where there was no evidence that individuals had been
695 selected based on their characteristics (22, 23, 25-29) .

696

697 ***Classification of interventions***

698 All seven studies had a low risk of bias due to having clear classification of interventions reported (22, 23,
699 25-29).

700

701 ***Deviations from intended interventions***

702 All seven studies had a low risk of bias due to there being no evidence of deviations from the intended
703 interventions (15, 22, 23, 25-29).

704

705 ***Missing data***

706 For the primary outcome clinical malaria incidence, the single study reporting this outcome has a low risk
707 of bias for missing data (23). For the primary outcome parasite prevalence, two of the studies had a low
708 risk of bias for missing data (23, 25); however the third study had a serious rating due to the low and
709 differential rates of missing data between the intervention groups (22). For the outcome density of
710 immature mosquitoes, all five studies had a low risk of bias due to missing data (22, 26-29). For the
711 outcome density of adult mosquitoes, both studies reporting this outcome has a low risk of bias due to
712 missing data (22, 26). For the outcome Entomological inoculation rate (EIR), the single study reporting this
713 outcome had a serious risk of bias due to differential rates of missing data between the intervention
714 groups and no analysis to assess the robustness to the presence of missing data (22).

715

716 ***Measurement of outcomes***

717 For the primary outcome clinical malaria incidence, the single study reporting this outcome has a low risk
718 of bias for the measurement of outcomes (23). For the primary outcome parasite prevalence, all three
719 studies had a low risk of bias for measurement of outcomes (22, 23, 25). For the outcome density of
720 immature mosquitoes, all five studies had a low risk of bias for measurement of outcomes (22, 26-29). For
721 the outcome density of adult mosquitoes, both studies reporting this outcome has a low risk of bias for
722 measurement of outcomes (22, 26). For the outcome Entomological inoculation rate (EIR), the single study
723 reporting this outcome had a low risk of bias for measurement of outcomes (22).

724

725 ***Selection of the reported result***

726 For the primary outcome clinical malaria incidence, the single study reporting this outcome has a
727 moderate risk of bias due to separate analyses being reported for children 1-5 years and all populations
728 (23). For the primary outcome parasite prevalence, two of the studies had a low risk of bias (23, 25);

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729 however the third study had a moderate rating due to separate analyses being reported for children 1-5
 730 years and all populations (22). For the outcome density of immature mosquitoes, two studies had a low
 731 risk of bias (22, 26); however the remaining three studies had a moderate risk of bias due to presenting
 732 separate analyses for either upstream and downstream results (27), for different larval stages (29), or for
 733 each village (28). For the outcome density of adult mosquitoes, both studies reporting this outcome has
 734 a low risk of bias (22, 26). For the outcome Entomological inoculation rate (EIR), the single study reporting
 735 this outcome had a low risk of bias (22).
 736
 737

738
 739 *Figure 5.* Risk of Bias traffic light plot of included studies with non-randomised designs (ROBINS-I) for
 740 primary outcome, clinical malaria incidence
 741

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742

743 *Figure 6. Risk of bias traffic light plot of included studies with non-randomised designs (ROBINS-I) for*
744 *primary outcome, parasite prevalence*

745

746

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747 *Figure 7.* Risk of bias traffic light plot of included studies with non-randomised designs (ROBINS-I) for
 748 secondary outcome, density of immature mosquitoes
 749

750
 751 *Figure 8.* Risk of bias traffic light plot of included studies with non-randomised designs (ROBINS-I) for
 752 secondary outcome, density of adult mosquitoes
 753

754
 755 *Figure 9.* Risk of bias traffic light plot of included studies with non-randomised designs (ROBINS-I) for
 756 secondary outcome, Entomological inoculation rate (EIR)
 757

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758 The remaining study, which used an uncontrolled design, was classified as having a critical overall risk of
759 bias due to the lack of a comparator group (30) for the secondary outcome measure, density of adult
760 mosquitoes.

761

762 **Effects of interventions**

763 The results from the studies are categorised into the type of intervention (habitat manipulation, habitat
764 modification, combination of habitat manipulation and modification), the specific type of manipulation /
765 modification, and the purpose of the intervention (LSM, non-LS).

766

767 ***Comparison 1. Habitat manipulation versus no intervention***

768

769 ***a. Water management approach:***

770 Two cluster randomised controlled trials and three controlled before-after study evaluated the effect of
771 habitat manipulation using water management (using either spillways, floodgates, different drawn down
772 rates of water, or different flooding and draining regimens) versus no intervention (19, 21-23, 27). Four
773 studies reported entomological outcomes (19, 21, 22, 27) and two studies reported the epidemiological
774 outcomes, malaria parasite prevalence (22, 23) and clinical malaria incidence (23). The findings from the
775 studies were (Supplementary Table 4a):

- 776 • Floodgates on a bed dam may reduce mosquito larval abundance downstream compared to no
777 intervention ((27), low certainty of evidence)
- 778 • It is uncertain whether the use of flood gates compared to no intervention reduces malaria
779 incidence or parasite prevalence because the certainty of this evidence is very low ((23), very low
780 certainty of evidence).
- 781 • Faster drawdown rates of water probably reduce the density of immature mosquitoes compared
782 to no drawdown of water ((21), moderate certainty of evidence)
- 783 • It is uncertain whether the use of spillways across streams reduces malaria parasite prevalence
784 compared to no intervention because the certainty of evidence is very low ((22), very low
785 certainty of evidence); however, spillways probably reduce the density of immature and adult
786 mosquitoes ((22), moderate certainty of evidence)
- 787 • Using intermittent irrigation of rice fields results probably results in a greater absolute density of
788 immature mosquitoes compared to continuously flooding ((19), moderate certainty of evidence)
- 789

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790 The study descriptions and findings of the individual studies are presented below in alphabetical order
791 based on the first author of the study.

792

793 **Kibret 2018 (21)**

794 **Study description:** This cluster randomised controlled trial assessed the effectiveness of water level
795 management as a habitat manipulation intervention with the purpose to target larvae habiting natural
796 ground pools approximately 1m in radius with a depth of 2m. The ground pool was constructed primarily
797 for hydropower generation and flood control. The trial was conducted in a high-risk malaria rural and
798 semi-arid area in central Ethiopia (Africa), in a town around the Koka reservoir. Twelve half-cones shaped
799 experimental ground pools were built, and three water drawdown treatments were applied (10 mm per
800 day, 15 mm per day, and 20 mm per day). The control group was comprised of three new built
801 experimental ground pools with no water-level drawdown. The larvae of the main vectors, *An. arabiensis*
802 and *An. pharoensis*, inhabited shoreline puddles and rain pools. No information regarding whether a co-
803 intervention was used was reported. The outcome measures assessed were density of immature
804 mosquitoes. Larvae were collected with a 350 ml standard dipping method and identification of larval
805 species was based on morphological characteristics. Anopheline larval density was expressed as the
806 number of larvae per m² of experimental ground pool wetted surface area.

807 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = some concerns):** Compared with the control, the density of
808 immature mosquitoes was generally reduced by 30% (OR = 0.70; $P < 0.05$), 70% (OR = 0.29; $P < 0.05$) and
809 84% (OR = 0.16; $P < 0.05$) with increasing draw down rates of water, respectively, during the main
810 transmission season.

811

812 **Mutero 2000 (19)**

813 **Study description:** This cluster randomised controlled trial was performed in Kenya near Nairobi in a rural
814 area within the Mwea Irrigation and Agricultural Development (MIAD) experimental station. The purpose
815 of the intervention was to target larvae inhabiting irrigated rice fields without adversely affecting rice
816 yield. Different water regimes were evaluated based on using 16 experimental subplots from 4 cluster
817 plots, over a 12-week period:

818 A) Continuously flooding, no rice planted (control, usual intervention)

819 B) Rice planted under drained conditions, flooded after transplanting

820 C) Rice transplanted under flood conditions, flooded after transplanting

821 D) Rice transplanted under drained conditions, intermittent irrigation after transplanting

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822 The main vector in the area was *An. arabiensis*. No information regarding whether a co-intervention was
823 used was reported. The outcome measure reported was the density of immature mosquitoes. Larval
824 sampling was conducted on two occasions prior to transplanting of rice seedlings. Sampling was then
825 conducted every week on two consecutive days in each subplot. They used a dipping collection method,
826 the sampling unit was 350 ml of water, 20 samples for each subplot and then larvae were pooled and
827 counted.

828 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = high risk):** The total number of larvae collected was the greatest
829 in plots using intermittent irrigation (D, n=4306), followed by water regime B (drained then flooded) and
830 C (flooded then flooded), continuous flooding (control) resulted in the lowest number of larvae (A, n=425)
831 (insufficient data to allow for statistical analysis).

832

833 **Santiago 1960 (22)**

834 **Study description:** This controlled before-after study was performed in the Philippines, in two urban and
835 coastal areas of South Pablo city. The purpose of the intervention was to control larvae in two streams,
836 which were the main larval habitats. The intervention comprised of the use of automatic siphons over two
837 main streams over distances of 1073m and 2897m downstream, which were repaired and recondition as
838 part of the study. The comparator comprised of an area where no flushing was performed (control area).
839 The predominant vector, *An. minimus flavirostris*, was found to mainly inhabit streams. No information
840 regarding whether a co-intervention was used was reported. Outcomes assessed were malaria parasite
841 prevalence, density of immature mosquitoes, density of adult mosquitoes, and entomological inoculation
842 rate (EIR). Malaria parasite prevalence in children from 2-10 years of age were tested once a year, for
843 three consecutive years during the same month. Larvae were sampled every 15 days and adult mosquitoes
844 were collected with human and animal (buffalo)-baited traps every fortnight. Entomological inoculation
845 rate was assessed in children under 1 years of age.

846 **Malaria parasite prevalence (RoB = serious risk):** There was no significant difference in malaria parasite
847 prevalence in children aged 2-10 years between the intervention areas during the two years at baseline
848 (31/560 versus 11/277; RR 1.39, 95% CI 0.71 to 2.73), however, a significant decrease in prevalence was
849 observed during the first year of intervention (0/586 versus 24/280, RR 0.01, 95% CI 0.00 to 0.16).

850 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = serious risk):** The monthly mean density of larvae per dip in the
851 intervention area decreased from a mean of 1.40 (standard deviation [SD], 0.25) to 0.059 (SD 0.20) and in
852 the control area from a mean of 0.7 (SD 0.30) to 0.49 (SD 0.15), resulting in a significant reduction of mean
853 density of 0.43 (95% CI 0.30 to 0.56).

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854 **Density of adult mosquitoes (RoB = serious risk):** The mean density of adult mosquitoes per month in the
855 intervention area reduced by 0.4 (from 0.4 to 0.0) but no change was observed in the control area (0.3);
856 (insufficient data to statistically compare or estimate effect size).

857 **Entomological inoculation rate (EIR) (RoB = serious risk):** At pre-intervention there was no significant
858 difference in the EIR in children under 1 years of age between the intervention and control groups (4/175
859 versus 2/54, RR 0.62, 95% CI 0.12 to 3.28). However, there was some evidence of a difference in EIR during
860 the first year of intervention (0/222 versus 3.83, RR 0.05, 95% CI 0.00 to 1.03).

861

862 **Sahu 2014 (27)**

863 **Study description:** This controlled before-after study (27) was conducted in a high malaria transmission
864 area, hilly and forested rural area in the Koraput district, Odisha (India), where two villages were selected
865 as intervention and control groups. The purpose of the intervention was to target larvae inhabiting areas
866 downstream of the bed-dams, which were constructed across streams. The intervention group comprised
867 of the use of floodgates using two sluice gates, which were opened and closed weekly, on a bed dam that
868 was 15 m long with a height of 4.5 m. The control group comprised had no floodgate, on a bed dam that
869 was 15 m in length and 1.5 m in height. The predominant vector in the area, *An. fluviatilis*, mainly
870 inhabited streams. The co-intervention used was unclear, but possible consisted of IRS using DDT. The
871 outcome measure reported was density of immature mosquitoes. Per dip density of *An. fluviatilis*
872 immatures (total number/total number of dips taken) were calculated. Immatures were reared to adults
873 for species identification. Prior to the construction of bed-dam, immatures were sampled at fortnightly
874 interval, while post-construction sampling was performed weekly. During each survey, 100 dips were
875 taken over a stretch of 500m from upstream and from downstream of the dam.

876 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = serious risk):** Baseline data showed similar densities of immature
877 mosquitoes between the intervention and control group, for both upstream (range in number per dip:
878 intervention: 0-0.05, control: 0.01-0.03) and downstream of the intervention arm (range in number per
879 dip: intervention: 0.02-0.04, control: 0-0.02). In the post-intervention period, a significant decrease in the
880 density of immature mosquitoes between the intervention and control groups was seen downstream
881 ($p < 0.01$), but no significant difference was seen upstream.

882

883 **Sharma 2008 (23)**

884 **Study description:** This controlled before-after study was conducted in Orissa (India) in three similar rural
885 villages (one selected for the intervention [271 participants] and two for the comparator group [299

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886 participants]) characterized by ethnic tribal communities with poor socio-economic status. A small
887 concrete dam (25 m length and 4 m height) was constructed across the stream in the village to provide
888 water for irrigation. The dam was fitted with three operational floodgates using sluice gates fitted at a
889 height of 4 m from ground level, which may be opened during the rainy season for discharge of excess
890 water. Therefore, the purpose of the intervention (use of floodgates) was for irrigation and to discharge
891 excess water, and thus not to target larvae inhabiting areas downstream of the dam and floodgates. The
892 primary vectors were *An. fluviatilis*, which were found to inhabit streams, and *An. culicifacies*, which were
893 found to inhabit stagnant pools, ditches and irrigation channels. The co-intervention used was routine
894 malaria control activities under the primary health care system which included yearly IRS with DDT and
895 there was a single round of IRS with a synthetic pyrethroid in alternate years. The outcome measures
896 reported were clinical malaria incidence and parasite prevalence (primary outcomes). Both passive and
897 weekly active surveillance of clinical malaria were conducted. Trained workers (one per village) were going
898 house to house once a week testing people found to have an axillary temperature of $>37.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ or a history
899 of fever in the previous 48 hrs, collecting thick and thin blood smears from finger pricks. Parasite
900 prevalence were collected via three cross-sectional surveys each year. 40% of households per village were
901 randomly selected and all age groups were considered during the process. Microscopic examination from
902 finger prick blood was used as the test, and result confirmation was given by a malaria clinic.

903 **Clinical malaria incidence (RoB = serious risk):** Differences in baseline rates of clinical malaria were seen
904 between the intervention and control groups in all participants (643.9/1000 versus 274.8/1000) and
905 children aged 1-5 years (1304.3/1000 versus 785.7/1000). Following construction, a significant reduction
906 of malaria incidence was reported between the intervention and control groups in children aged 1-5 years
907 (181.8/1000 versus 1000/1000) ($p<0.01$).

908 **Parasite prevalence (RoB = serious risk):** Malaria parasite rate in the pre-intervention period was similar
909 in the intervention and control group (17.6% and 18.9%; $p=0.75$). Following the construction of the dam,
910 the study reported a significant decrease in rates in the intervention village ($p<0.01$) but no significant
911 decline in the control villages ($p>0.05$).

912

913 **b. Shading management approach:**

914 One randomised controlled trial and two non-randomised controlled studies assessed the effect of
915 shading management as a habitat manipulation intervention compared to no intervention (17, 28, 29).
916 Only entomological outcomes were reported. Shading of drainage channels using Napier grass reduces
917 densities of immature mosquitoes compared to no intervention ((17, 29), high certainty of evidence).

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918 Shading using unweeded rice habitats, or providing coverage using arrow root or water ferns may reduce
919 density of immature mosquitoes compared to no intervention ((29), low certainty of evidence)
920 (Supplementary Table 4b).

921

922 **Imbahale 2011 (29)**

923 **Study description:** This non-randomised intervention study (29) assessed the effect of three intervention
924 types on vector control in a semi-urban and low-income area in Western Kenya. The purpose of the
925 intervention was to target larvae inhabiting irrigated agriculture. For this comparison, two habitat types
926 were considered. The first intervention type was shading with local plants, which was introduced in 30
927 non-randomly selected larval habitats (1 metre × 1 metre × 0.5 metres) by building a shallow dyke (0.2 m)
928 around each habitat and comparing this to six further habitats which were left unplanted (control). Each
929 of the four locally grown plant species, Napier grass (*Pennisetum purpureum*), arrowroot (*Maranta*
930 *arudinacea*), papyrus reeds (*Cyperus spp.*), weeded and unweeded rice (*Oryza sativa*), were planted in
931 each intervention habitat and replicated six times. The second intervention type was plant cover inside or
932 along the banks of man-made water canals already present in the area. These included arrow root growing
933 along banks of water canals and inside water canals; sweet potatoes (*Ipomea batatas*) growing along
934 banks of water channels, African couch grass (*Cynodon dactylon*) growing inside water channels, and water
935 ferns (*Azolla filiculoides*) growing on the water surface and comparing these to two open sites with no
936 plant cover (control). Each of the intervention and control habitats (2 metres x 0.75 metres x 0.3 metres)
937 was replicated five times. All habitats were irrigated by running water from large canals (20 metres away).
938 The malaria vectors were *An. gambiae*, *An. coustani*, and *An. funestus*. A standard dipping method was
939 used to collect immature mosquitoes, collected on a weekly basis. Larvae were recorded either as early
940 instars (L1 and L2) or late instars (L3 and L4), and mosquito density was expressed as number of larvae
941 per dip. No co-intervention was used.

942 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = serious risk):** Significant reductions in the density of early instars
943 of anophelines (all species) were seen for shading with Napier grass (Odds Ratio [OR] 0.41, 95% CI 0.24 to
944 0.72), unweeded rice habitats (OR 0.49, 95% CI 0.25 to 0.96), and arrowroot habitats (OR 0.58, 95% CI
945 0.33 to 1.00) compared with control. Significant reductions in late-stage larvae were seen for unweeded
946 rice habitats (OR 0.09, 95% CI 0.01 to 0.76) and arrowroot habitats (OR 0.05, 95% CI 0.01 to 0.38), but not
947 for Napier grass (OR 0.50, 95% CI 0.18 to 1.41) compared with the control. *An. gambiae* s.l. was mostly
948 found in open habitats (control), while habitats with water ferns recorded the lowest density. *An. funestus*
949 was mainly recorded in habitats with African couch grass. The abundance of both early and late instar

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950 larvae of anophelines were significantly reduced in habitats covered with water ferns (early instar: OR
951 0.29, 95% CI 0.14 to 0.58; late instar: OR 0.26, 95% CI 0.08 to 0.85).

952

953 **Imbahale 2012 (28)**

954 **Study description:** This non-randomised controlled intervention study (28) assessed the effect of two
955 intervention types on vector control in two rural highland villages in Western Kenya, drainage (previously
956 described above) and shading with arrowroot. The purpose of the intervention was to target larvae
957 inhabiting a range of temporary and permanent habits ranging from grand pools to drainage canals. For
958 this comparison, one intervention type was considered, shading with arrowroot, which was compared to
959 no intervention (control). The interventions implemented depended on the suitability of the habitat, and
960 this intervention was only implemented in six habitats in one village. The main vectors were *An. gambiae*
961 s.l, *An. arabiensis*, and *An. funestus*. A standard dipping method was used to collect immature mosquitoes,
962 collected on a weekly basis. Larvae were recorded either as early instars or late instars and mosquito
963 density was expressed as number of larvae per dip. With regards to the co-intervention used this was the
964 Roll Back Malaria initiative, which comprised of ITNs, IRS and anti-malarial drugs.

965 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = moderate risk):** The mean densities of early and late instars were
966 zero in the habitats provided with arrow root; therefore no statistical testing could be performed.

967

968 **Wamae 2010 (17)**

969 **Study description:** This randomised controlled trial (17) was conducted in two rural villages in Western
970 Kenya. The purpose of the intervention was to target larvae inhabiting irrigated agriculture. The
971 intervention comprised of shading 11 drainage channels with Napier grass which was planted on both
972 sides of the entire length of the channel. The comparator group included 11 drainage channels which had
973 no intervention (control). Usual farm activities, including occasional cleaning, drainage, and land
974 cultivation, continued uninterrupted during the conduct of the trial. The vectors collected in the area were
975 *An. gambiae* s.l, *An. funestus*, *An. coustani*, *An. rufipes*, *An. marshalli*, *An. maculipalpis*, *An. azaniae*, *An.*
976 *implexus*. Standard dipping method was used to collect immature mosquitoes, which happened once
977 every week. No co-intervention was used.

978 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = some concerns):** A significant reduction in the mean number of
979 *An. gambiae* larvae was seen between the intervention and control groups within each village (village 1:
980 78.4% reduction ANOVA, $p < 0.0001$; village 2: 88.0% reduction, ANOVA, $p < 0.0001$). Additionally, the

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981 intervention resulted in a significant reduction in the mean number (density) of all anopheline spp. within
982 each village (village 1: 75.4% reduction, ANOVA, $p < 0.0001$; village 2: 88.4% reduction, ANOVA, $p < 0.0001$).
983

984 **c. Other/combination management approaches:**

985 One cluster randomised controlled trial assessed the effect of disturbance of the larval habitat as a habitat
986 manipulation intervention (20). Only entomological outcomes were reported. Frequent and intermediate
987 disturbance of habitats through clearing grass and replenishing water from local streams increases the
988 density of immature mosquitoes compared to no intervention ((20), high certainty of evidence,
989 Supplementary Table 4c).

990

991 **Munga 2013 (20)**

992 **Study description:** The cluster randomised controlled trial (20) was performed in a hilly rural village in
993 western Kenya, characterized by cultivated and uncultivated areas. The purpose of the intervention was
994 to target larvae inhabiting areas in a low-lying area near a stream. The study had three arms. A total of 30
995 larval habitats were randomly assigned to one of two interventions with 10 replicates each, or one control
996 with 10 replicates. Habitats in the intervention groups were cleared of grass and had water replenishment
997 from the local stream either every 10 days (frequent disturbance), or every 20 days (intermediate
998 disturbance). The habitats in the control group were left undisturbed (no clearing of grass and no water
999 replenishment). Six replicates (phases) of the same experiment were conducted, each phase lasted for 30
1000 days, in between each phase the control group habitats were also cleared of grass before the experiment
1001 was repeated. The primary vectors found in the area were *An. gambiae*, *An. funestus*, *An. coustani* and
1002 *An. Implexus*; however, larval means were only presented for the main vector, *An. gambiae*. A standard
1003 dipping method was used to collect immature mosquitoes and collection happened daily. No co-
1004 intervention was used.

1005 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = some concerns):** There was a 1.7 fold increase in larvae in
1006 frequently disturbed habitats ($p < 0.001$) and 1.3 times increase in larvae in intermediate disturbed habitats
1007 ($p < 0.05$) compared to non-disturbed habitats.

1008

1009 **Comparison 2. Habitat manipulation with larviciding versus no intervention**

1010 Two controlled before-after studies evaluated the effect of water management as a habitat manipulation
1011 (24, 25). Both studies reported epidemiological outcomes; however, only one study reported
1012 entomological outcomes (24). Repairing and clearing of drains, cutting grasses and making minor repairs

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1013 (e.g. slab replacement) combined with larviciding may reduce malaria parasite prevalence compared to
1014 no intervention ((25), low certainty of evidence, Supplementary Table 4d). It is not clear whether
1015 encouraging the community to eliminate domestic larval habitat sites had an impact on vector control
1016 due to insufficient uptake of the intervention ((24), risk of bias: critical).

1017

1018 **Castro 2009 (25)**

1019 **Study description:** This controlled before-after study (25) was performed in a city of 9070 people in
1020 Tanzania. The purpose of the intervention was to target larvae inhabiting drains. This was a three-armed
1021 study. A total of six sites were included in the study, which ran for 12 months. Within the intervention
1022 group, which were located at two sites, drains in the city were repaired and cleared to increase the water
1023 flow and to reduce flooding in the rainy season; additionally, grasses were cut, and minor repairs made
1024 (e.g. slab replacement). Two further sites received larviciding throughout the 12 months study period. The
1025 final two sites comprised the control group, which received no intervention for the 12 months study
1026 period. At the end of the 12 months period, all six sites received larviciding. Results were only presented
1027 for the comparison of two groups - habitat manipulation with larviciding versus no intervention. The main
1028 vectors in the area were: *An. gambiae*, *An. funestus* and *An. coustani*. The co-intervention used was IRS
1029 with DDT. The outcome measure reported was malaria parasite prevalence. Six surveys, one every other
1030 month were performed with 75 houses randomly selected and 4 people in each house (2 adults, 2
1031 children). A total of 3203 and 2989 individuals were tested in the two intervention and control group
1032 respectively. Analysis was adjusted for age, rainfall, bed net use, and larviciding use after the end of the
1033 12 months study period.

1034 **Malaria parasite prevalence (RoB = moderate risk):** At the end of the study, the intervention sites had a
1035 significant lower odds of malaria parasite prevalence than compared to the control group had a
1036 significantly higher risk of malaria parasite infection (adjusted OR 0.59, 95% CI 0.42 to 0.83).

1037

1038 **Samnotra 1980 (24)**

1039 **Study description:** This controlled before-after study (24) was performed in two villages (intervention
1040 village, approximately 92,000 participants; control village, approximately 5,000 participants) in an urban
1041 area in India, where *An. culicifacies* and *An. stephensi* are the main vectors and malaria transmission is
1042 considered low. The intervention group village was divided into two sectors and each sector was divided
1043 into six sections. The purpose of the intervention was to target larvae inhabiting a range of domestic sites.
1044 Households were encouraged to reduce or remove domestic larval habitat sites, including tanks, pitchers,

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1045 and cisterns. Additionally, the intervention group received larviciding of non-domestic larval habitat sites
1046 within the village were performed on a weekly basis. The control village was divided into five sections and
1047 received no intervention. The co-intervention used was case management and treatment for fever cases.
1048 Although the outcome measures reported were clinical malaria incidence, malaria parasite prevalence
1049 (primary outcomes), density of immature mosquitoes, and the density of adult mosquitoes (secondary
1050 outcomes), the attempt to encourage households in the intervention group to perform habitat
1051 manipulation was not successful, and as a consequence, the results from this study reflected solely the
1052 effect of larviciding compared to no intervention, which is beyond the scope of this review (risk of bias:
1053 critical).

1054

1055 **Comparison 3. Combination of habitat manipulation and modification versus no intervention**

1056 One controlled before-after study (26) and one non-randomised controlled intervention study (28)
1057 assessed the effect of the combination of habitat manipulation and modification versus no intervention.
1058 Only entomological outcomes were reported. The findings from the studies were (Supplementary Table
1059 4e):

- 1060 • Construction of drainage canals, planting of papyrus and other reeds for shading near dams
1061 probably reduces the density of adult mosquitoes compared to no intervention ((26), moderate
1062 certainty of evidence).
- 1063 • Preventing water stagnating using drainage of canals, removal of debris, land levelling, and filling
1064 ditches with soil reduces the density of immature mosquitoes compared to no intervention ((28),
1065 high certainty of evidence).

1066

1067 **Yohannes 2005 (26)**

1068 **Study description:** This controlled before-after study (26) was performed in two villages in a rural highland
1069 area in Ethiopia. The purpose of the intervention was to target larvae inhabiting a range of habits. The
1070 intervention focused on draining the base of the dam embankment, construction of drainage canals,
1071 prohibition and filling of crossing points of cattle and human along riverbed to prevent the destruction of
1072 plants and the creation of larval habitat sites with hoof-footprints, planting of papyrus and other reeds to
1073 create shading. All activities were carried out by the local community. *An. arabiensis* and other
1074 anophelines (species not specified) were found inhabiting in the area. The outcome measures reported
1075 were the density of immature mosquitoes and the density of adult mosquitoes (secondary outcome).
1076 Larval collection was performed with standard dipping method twice monthly, up to 10 dips were made

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1077 in each type of water body encountered at each survey. Adult mosquitoes were collected using CDC light
1078 traps, knockdown collections and window exit traps in 30 randomly chosen houses/month. Human-
1079 landing catches, indoors and outdoors, (8 houses/month, two houses for four consecutive nights) were
1080 also performed. Adult anophelines were counted and identified to species based on morphological
1081 descriptions. *Anopheles gambiae* s.l. were identified by polymerase chain reaction. Data were only
1082 presented for light traps on *An. arabiensis*. IRS with DDT was used during the pre-intervention phase.

1083 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = serious risk):** During the intervention, a general reduction in the
1084 total number (density) of third and fourth instars (119 vs 673) and all larval stages (163 vs 720) belonging
1085 to *An. arabiensis* was observed in the intervention village compared to the baseline phase; however, no
1086 statistical testing was performed to compare the change in the density of larvae between the intervention
1087 groups.

1088 **Density of adult mosquitoes (RoB = serious risk):** A 49% significant relative reduction in the mean number
1089 (density) of adult mosquitoes was seen in the intervention village, after controlling for the change in the
1090 control village (95% confidence interval 46.6% to 50%; intervention village: geometric mean 4.01 to 0.66;
1091 control village: geometric mean 0.63 to 0.20).

1092

1093 **Imbahale 2012 (28)**

1094 **Study description:** This non-randomised controlled intervention study (28) assessed the effect of two
1095 intervention types on vector control in two rural highland villages in western Kenya. For this comparison,
1096 one intervention type was considered, a combination of habitat manipulation and modification, which
1097 included drainage of canals, removal of debris, land levelling, or filling ditches with soil to prevent any
1098 water stagnating. The purpose of the intervention was to target larvae inhabiting a range of temporary
1099 and permanent habits ranging from grand pools to drainage canals. This intervention was compared to
1100 no intervention (control). The interventions implemented depended on the suitability of the habitat. In
1101 each village both interventions were performed. The main vectors were *An. gambiae* s.l, *An. arabiensis*,
1102 and *An. funestus*. A standard dipping method was used to collect immature mosquitoes, collected on a
1103 weekly basis. Larvae were recorded either as early instars or late instars and mosquito density was
1104 expressed as number of larvae per dip. With regards to the co-intervention used, this was the Roll Back
1105 Malaria initiative, which comprised of ITNs, IRS and anti-malarial drugs.

1106 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = moderate risk):** In one village, the abundance of early and late
1107 instar *Anopheles* were less likely to be sampled from drainage habitats (early instars: OR 0.45, $p < 0.05$; late
1108 instars: OR 0.13, $p < 0.05$) compared to control habitats. However, in the second village, only late instars

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1109 were less likely to be sampled from drainage habitats (OR 0.90; $p < 0.05$) compared to control habitats,
1110 with no significant effect seen for early instars (OR 0.91; $p > 0.05$).

1111

1112 **Comparison 4. Habitat manipulation and modification with larviciding versus no intervention**

1113 One cluster-randomised controlled trial (18) and one uncontrolled before-after study (30) evaluated the
1114 combination effects of habitat manipulation and modification with larviciding compared to no
1115 intervention. Only the results from the cluster-randomised controlled trial are considered, which reported
1116 only entomological outcomes (18). Filling, drainage, or elimination of rain pools and puddles at water
1117 supply points and stream pools bedded with sediment probably reduces the density of immature and
1118 adult mosquitoes when delivered with larviciding compared to no intervention ((18), moderate certainty
1119 of evidence, Supplementary Table 4f).

1120

1121 **Shililu 2007 (18)**

1122 **Study description:** This cluster-randomised controlled trial (18) was conducted in a rural area in Eritrea,
1123 in eight villages from four selected zones. The purpose of the intervention was to target larvae inhabiting
1124 a range of habits. The intervention comprised of filling, drainage, or elimination of rain pools and puddles
1125 at water supply points and stream pools bedded with sediment, together with larviciding. The control
1126 arms had no intervention. Two villages were randomly selected from each of the four selected zones to
1127 act as intervention and control sites. Several vectors were found in the area: *An. arabiensis*, *An. cinereus*,
1128 *An. pretoriensis*, *An. d'thali*, *An. funestus*, *An. squamosus*, *An. adenensis* and *An. demeilloni*. The outcome
1129 measures reported were the density of immature mosquitoes and the density of adult mosquitoes. Larvae
1130 were collected using standard dipping technique (350 ml dipper) and 10 to 20 dips were taken in each
1131 larval habitat. Larval densities were expressed as number of larvae per 10 dips because the numbers of
1132 larvae were low. Twelve CDC miniature light traps (indoor/outdoor) were placed from dusk to dawn (12
1133 hours), for two consecutive days per week, with six traps placed within each village. *An. arabiensis* density
1134 is expressed as number of mosquitoes per light trap. No co-interventions were used; however, ITNs and
1135 IRS were conducted as part of the national malaria control program (coverage not stated).

1136 **Density of immature mosquitoes (RoB = some concerns):** A significant reduction in the mean larval density
1137 was reported in the intervention villages compared to control villages (ANOVA, $p < 0.001$), where in one
1138 zone, the mean number] of larvae was smaller in the intervention compared to the control villages (mean
1139 number [\pm Standard Deviation, SD]: 0.87 ± 0.04 versus 3.17 ± 0.11 , respectively).

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1140 **Density of adult mosquitoes (RoB = some concerns):** A significant reduction in the total number (density)
1141 of adult *An. arabiensis* was seen in the intervention villages compared to control villages (ANOVA, $p < 0.05$;
1142 data on adult densities not reported).

1143

1144 **Lee 2010 (30)**

1145 **Study description (RoB = critical risk):** This uncontrolled before-after study (30) was conducted over a two
1146 year period on Tekong Island in Singapore (Japan), which is a rural area that is characterized by very low
1147 malaria endemicity, and the recognized vectors are *An. sudaicus* and *An. maculates*. The purpose of the
1148 intervention was to target larvae inhabiting forested areas. The active intervention was shoreline works,
1149 drainage, maintenance of drains vegetation clearing and filling up pools of water, delivered as part of an
1150 integrated malaria control program which also included larviciding and adulticiding, IRS, preventing the
1151 importation of malaria (where an eight week quarantine was imposed on individuals returning from
1152 malaria endemic countries and screening for foreigners), early detection of human cases of malaria,
1153 personal protection measures, and having a contingency plan in case of an outbreak of malaria. No co-
1154 interventions were used. The study reported the density of adult mosquitoes, where human landing
1155 catches were used to trap mosquitoes every week for the first six months, then fortnightly in 60 fixed sites
1156 and then at the same frequency but in 40 sites only. There was a 94% reduction in the mean number of
1157 all genera of mosquitoes per site post-intervention compared to densities before, although the proportion
1158 of *Anopheles* mosquitoes remained low and changed marginally throughout the intervention period
1159 (1.63% to 1.32%). The design of this study means that the effect of the intervention cannot be determined.

1160

1161 **DISCUSSION**

1162

1163 This systematic review included 14 studies and one on-going study. Of the included studies, five used a
1164 randomised controlled trial design, of which, four used a cluster-design; six used a controlled before-after
1165 study design, three used a non-randomised controlled design, and one used an uncontrolled before-after
1166 study design. Three studies reported epidemiological outcomes and 10 studies reported entomological
1167 outcomes. None of the studies reported on the environmental impacts associated with the intervention.
1168 None of the included studies had a low overall risk of bias.

1169

1170 **Summary of main results**

1171

1172 ***Habitat manipulation only***

1173 The evidence for the use of floodgates on a dam or spillways across streams tended to range from very
1174 low to low, with very low evidence relating to their use on the impact of malaria incidence or parasite
1175 prevalence compared to no intervention (22, 23). However, the evidence tended to range from low to
1176 moderate for the impact of floodgates and spillways on the density of immature and adult mosquitoes
1177 (22, 27). Faster water drawdown rates were found to probably reduce mosquito larval abundance, with a
1178 moderate level of certainty; however its effect on the malaria risk to human populations surrounding
1179 dams has not been assessed (21).

1180

1181 Habitat manipulation through shading of water sources using specific plants has the potential as a malaria
1182 mosquito control tool; however, its effect on epidemiological outcomes has not been assessed. For
1183 example, the shading of drainage channels using Napier grass (in areas where this can be grown) was
1184 shown to improve larval control with high certainty (17, 29). This is likely to be due to the reduction in
1185 sunlight and water temperature and lowering algae production, thereby decreasing larval development
1186 and survival. Although overall reductions in larval populations were seen in habitats where shading was
1187 provided by other local plants (rice, arrowroots, water ferns), the certainty of this evidence was low (29).

1188

1189 Intermittent irrigation in an existing irrigation system should not be recommended unless it is
1190 appropriately implemented since based on the evidence within the systematic review, the greatest yield
1191 of larvae was found in this water regimen, while continuous flooding resulted in the lowest yield (19(19)).
1192 Therefore, it is suggested that only periodic active drainage of rice fields is used, and since this usually
1193 requires substantial labour resources, it is recommended that such intervention only occurs during
1194 periods which are most critical in terms of mosquito densities; however, no epidemiological outcomes
1195 were assessed for this intervention.

1196

1197 Frequent and intermediate disturbance of larval habitats through clearing grass and replenishing water
1198 from local streams was shown, with high certainty, to negatively affect larval control compared to
1199 undisturbed habitats (20). Despite this, malaria vectors can be found in habitats with varying levels of
1200 water disturbance or the undisturbed ones. This could be related to the high effect of predation together
1201 with the development of algae in stable water. So, simple habitat manipulation approaches such as
1202 maintaining the drainage ditches could result in reductions in the abundance of mosquitoes.

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1203 The effect of repairing and clearing drains, cutting grasses and making minor repairs (e.g. slab
1204 replacement) had only low certainty of evidence for reducing malaria parasite prevalence as the
1205 intervention was combined with larviciding in the intervention group and therefore the independent
1206 effect of the habitat manipulation intervention could not be established (25). Additionally, it is not clear
1207 whether encouraging the community to eliminate domestic larval habitat sites had an impact on vector
1208 control due to insufficient uptake of the intervention (24).

1209

Combination of habitat manipulation and modification

1211 The combination of habitat of manipulation and modification through the construction of drainage canals
1212 and planting of papyrus and other reeds for shading near dams has the potential as a malaria mosquito
1213 control tool (26); however, its effect on epidemiological outcomes has not been assessed.

1214

1215 The review found, with high certainty of evidence, that the prevention of water stagnating using drainage
1216 of canals, removal of debris, land levelling, and filling ditches with soil was shown to probably reduce the
1217 density of immature mosquitoes (28); however, its effect on epidemiological outcomes has not been
1218 assessed.

1219

1220 The effect of filling, drainage, or elimination of rain pools and puddles at water supply points and stream
1221 pools bedded with sediment had only moderate certainty of evidence for reducing the densities of
1222 immature and adult mosquitoes as the intervention was combined with larviciding in the intervention
1223 group (18). Therefore, the independent effect of the combination of habitat manipulation and
1224 modification intervention could not be established; additionally, no studies have assessed its impact on
1225 epidemiological outcomes.

1226

Certainty of evidence

1228 We reviewed studies where habitat modification and manipulation were used as single or additional
1229 interventions to control malaria. The findings of this review indicated variable certainty of evidence when
1230 considering habitat modification and manipulation as interventions to control malaria vectors. Only a
1231 limited number of studies reported epidemiological outcomes on malaria. Several factors were taken into
1232 account when assessing the certainty of the evidence including: the study design, the type of intervention,
1233 the length of the intervention, the type of outcome, the statistical analysis, the setting, the seasonality,
1234 the frequency of data collection, the presence of other biotic and abiotic factors influencing the results,

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1235 amongst others. We reported a summary of the main findings specifying how confident we are in
1236 confirming the effectiveness of the tested intervention(s) in that specific setting having assessed these
1237 factors.

1238

1239 **Overall completeness and applicability of evidence**

1240 This review demonstrates that there is currently not sufficient evidence regarding whether manipulation
1241 alone or in combination with modification, of larval habitats positively impacts human malaria cases or
1242 malaria transmission. In some cases, studies reported that the intervention under study may lead to a
1243 reduction in adult or immature mosquitoes. For those studies demonstrating marked impact on
1244 mosquitoes, data collected were limited in the breadth of settings and geographic areas where specific
1245 interventions were performed and so generalizing those results with positive outcomes for vector control
1246 to other areas should only be done with extreme caution. Moreover, in these cases, results simply show
1247 that the intervention may have a potential benefit worthy of further research. Only three studies reported
1248 epidemiological outcomes, and none had a low risk of bias, so it is difficult to use these to draw firm
1249 conclusions on the effect of tested interventions.

1250

1251 **Strengths, limitations and potential biases of the systematic review process**

1252 The strength of this systematic review is that a comprehensive search was conducted with two reviewers
1253 independently selecting studies, extracting data and assessing risk of bias, which minimises the risk of
1254 eligible studies being missed and inaccuracies in the reported results. Additionally, restrictions were not
1255 placed in terms of language. However, this systematic review has certain limitations. We were unable to
1256 perform meta-analyses to provide pooled estimates of the effectiveness of the interventions due to
1257 insufficient studies using similar interventions and insufficient reporting of the intervention effects, where
1258 most studies relied on reporting solely p values. This also meant that we were unable to formally assess
1259 the presence of publication bias and investigate reasons for heterogeneity using planned subgroup and
1260 sensitivity analyses. Furthermore, none of the included studies had a low overall risk of bias. The overall
1261 risk of bias of the RCTs was 'high' for one trial and 'some concerns' for the other trials, and the majority
1262 of the non-randomised intervention studies was deemed to have 'serious' risks of bias, with only two
1263 having 'moderate' risk of bias. We also included one uncontrolled before-after studies which had a
1264 'critical' risk of bias; however, results from this study were not reported in the summary of findings table.
1265 We contacted study authors where information was missing or unclear and where raw data were needed
1266 to perform further analysis, but it was unfruitful.

1267

1268 **Agreements/disagreements with other systematic reviews**

1269 In 2005, Keiser and colleagues (7) systematically reviewed the use of environmental management
1270 measures to reduce malaria. In this systematic review, only papers analysing epidemiological outcomes
1271 were included and most of them were dated and conducted before the Global Malaria Eradication
1272 Campaign (1955 to 1969); therefore, a limitation of this older review in comparison to our review is that
1273 it did not consider entomological outcomes. The Keiser and colleagues review concluded that clinical
1274 malaria morbidity and mortality were reduced regardless of whether environmental modification,
1275 environmental manipulation, or modification or manipulation of human habitation or behaviour, were
1276 used (7). In general, we are in agreement with this previous review in terms of emphasising the relevance
1277 of using LSM in addition to traditional interventions to reduce malaria when planning an integrated
1278 malaria control program. However, we judged the quality of data used to be very poor and therefore the
1279 conclusions of the review were not supported by a strong systematic review methodology, especially
1280 because no assessment of the quality of evidence was performed. A more recent review performed by
1281 Tusting and colleagues (8) reviewed the literature of the four LSM strategies and the inclusion criteria
1282 slightly differ from ours, as reported earlier in this report. A total of 13 studies were identified as meeting
1283 their inclusion criteria, but only six studies were evaluating habitat modification (one study) or
1284 manipulation (one study) interventions alone or in combination with the use of larvivorous fish or
1285 larviciding (four studies). We reconsidered and included these six studies in our review as they met our
1286 inclusion criteria; however, we did not agree with the authors of the Tusting and colleagues review
1287 regarding two of the studies. Specifically, for one study (15) we decided it was not appropriate to extract
1288 include the study because the effect of the intervention was limited to the application of larviciding, this
1289 is in contrast to Tusting and colleagues (8) who classified the paper as habitat modification plus larviciding.
1290 Additionally, the date of the construction of the intervention was not clearly stated (which seemed to be
1291 before the outcome data were collected and therefore could be considered as an observational study
1292 design). In the second study (24), given the information provided in the text on the failure in the attempt
1293 of performing habitat manipulation by the community, we think the results of the intervention should be
1294 totally addressed to larviciding. Therefore, we considered it inappropriate to extract data from this study,
1295 which is in contrast to Tusting and colleagues who reported the results as an integrated intervention
1296 (habitat manipulation plus larviciding). Additionally, in the review by Trusting and colleagues (8), the
1297 assessment of the risk of bias of the included studies was performed using a modified version of the
1298 Cochrane Effective Practice and Organisation of Care Risk of Bias guidelines (49). We elected to use the

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1299 Cochrane Risk of Bias 2.0 and the ROBINS-I tools for assessing the risk of bias in the included studies as
1300 these tools can be used directly without modification and also enable the risk of bias of non-randomised
1301 studies to be assessed based only on relevant domains (13). In general, we strongly agree with the
1302 conclusions of Tusting and colleagues regarding the majority of included studies were not conducted
1303 rigorously, data were not appropriately analyzed, there was a lack of negative or null studies, and finally
1304 that generalizing results with positive outcomes to areas different from the original place where they were
1305 performed should only be done with extreme caution. However, we also concluded that in specific Asian
1306 and African settings, LSM could be a good support for malaria control programs when appropriately
1307 adjusted to different circumstances.

1308

1309 World Health Organization recommendations

1310 The WHO considers environmental management (habitat modification and manipulation) as a potential
1311 strategy to control malaria by reducing larval habitats. The findings from this systematic review will inform
1312 the development of new WHO guidance in this area as stated in the last WHO Guidelines for Malaria
1313 Vector Control Guidelines (2). Many local programs are already implementing LSM strategies, including
1314 habitat modification and manipulation, to reduce malaria transmission often combining them with other
1315 core vector control interventions (e.g. IRS or LLINS) or additional LSM interventions, such as larviciding.
1316 Although this systematic review supports the effectiveness of certain permanent or temporary
1317 interventions of larval habitats within specific settings and on reducing mosquito numbers, it is difficult to
1318 recommend habitat manipulation/modification for malaria prevention and control without
1319 epidemiological evidence or sufficient studies demonstrating that a significant reduction in
1320 immature/adult mosquito vector densities translates directly into reduced clinical disease. Although it is
1321 acknowledged that there is a wealth of historical research on the environmental management of malaria,
1322 unfortunately this literature was insufficiently robust to be included in this systematic review. Therefore,
1323 further well-designed studies, using controlled before-after or randomised controlled design, are needed
1324 to evaluate the effectiveness of such interventions, particularly in relation to epidemiological outcomes
1325 relating to malaria. However, in the absence of such studies, national programmes may decide to use
1326 habitat manipulation and/or modification interventions to avoid the creation, and reduce the availability
1327 of larval habitats, where deemed appropriate, based on expert guidance and local knowledge.

1328

1329 Implications for practice

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1330 In Africa and Asia, habitat modification and manipulation when adequately performed could be
1331 considered as another option to control mosquito abundance alongside core interventions (LLINs or IRS);
1332 however, the evidence is too insufficient for their effectiveness of epidemiological outcomes. As an
1333 example, it can be stated with moderate certainty that spillways across streams and dams with increased
1334 drawdown rates decreased the density of larvae (21), that intermittent irrigation has a negative effect on
1335 mosquito control compared to continuous flooding (19), and that filling, drainage, or elimination of rain
1336 pools and puddles at water supply points or stream pools bedded with sediment (18) probably reduce
1337 adult or larval densities. With high certainty, we can promote the use of shading channels with specific
1338 local plants (17, 29), and the prevention of water stagnation through using drainage of canals, removal of
1339 debris, land levelling, and filling ditches with soil to reduce larval densities (28), but we cannot recommend
1340 the use of frequent and intermediate clearing of grass and replenishing water in larval habitats since it
1341 was found to have a negative impact on mosquito control (20). Unfortunately, we cannot recommend the
1342 use of other habitat management interventions assessed in this review, given the low or very low level of
1343 certainty of the studies; however, national programmes may decide to use habitat manipulation and/or
1344 modification interventions, where deemed appropriate, based on expert guidance and local knowledge.
1345 The increased engagement of communities has been emphasized in WHO's Global Technical Strategy
1346 2016–2030 (50) and many country national malaria strategic plans, using locally selected and trained
1347 volunteers(51). It was found to be a key element in many of the selected papers, and programs that inform
1348 communities and contribute to behaviour change to promote better and healthier environments are
1349 crucial for these activities and should be considered when officially planning these types of interventions.
1350 Inexpensive and simple methods to reduce mosquito larval abundance could complement other vector
1351 control methods, especially in areas where resources for core vector control interventions are scarce.

1352

1353 **Implications for future research**

1354

1355 Several of the included studies were conducted more than 30 years ago and the data collected together
1356 with the analyses reported were unclear or missing, so it was difficult to support with a good certainly
1357 many of the findings. Most of the study designs varied in the degree to which they allowed observed
1358 effects to be attributed to the intervention with confidence. Statistical comparisons between intervention
1359 and control groups were often missing, so it is not clear whether the effect of the intervention was
1360 significant as a vector control strategy. Furthermore, most of the studies collected data on entomological
1361 (secondary) outcomes; few studies with data recording the impact on malaria outcomes were available.

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1362 Based on these observations, further high-quality studies, preferably using either controlled before-after
1363 or randomised controlled designs assessing the effective of habitat manipulation +/- habitat modification
1364 should be conducted, which give more attention to different aspects of study design and data analysis.

1365 For example, studies should include:

- 1366 - baseline data of reported outcomes
- 1367 - a longer intervention/follow-up period to assess seasonal impacts
- 1368 - an evaluation of the short- and long-term effects of the intervention
- 1369 - appropriate randomization process in the assignment of intervention and control groups
- 1370 - two or more intervention and control arms
- 1371 - repetition of the same intervention in different settings and geographic areas
- 1372 - the use of the appropriate statistical methods to analyse data and compare intervention with
1373 control groups

1374 In addition, future studies need to prioritise collecting data on primary epidemiological outcomes
1375 (clinical malaria incidence, malaria parasite prevalence, malaria parasitaemia incidence, incidence of
1376 severe malaria, anaemia prevalence, mean haemoglobin levels (g/dl), mortality rate due to malaria, and
1377 hospital admissions for malaria) instead of secondary entomological outcomes alone. It is
1378 acknowledged that this can incur a higher cost to the study but would allow for better assessment of
1379 the epidemiological impact of larval habitat manipulation and modification to guide future World
1380 Health Organization recommendations.

1381

1382 **Differences between protocol and review**

1383 As described in the methods section, initially we were to include cluster randomised trials (cRCT) which
1384 had at least two intervention and two comparator sites, and CBA studies which had at least two
1385 intervention and two comparator sites. However, we relaxed the number of sites condition as there
1386 were insufficient cRCT and CBA studies identified for each type of interventions. We anticipated being
1387 able to summarise the effects of interventions on adverse events as an outcome measure; however,
1388 this became impractical and no studies were identified which reported environmental and health
1389 impacts affecting either human or animal populations, such as changes to biodiversity and ecosystem
1390 due to active intervention of the habitat. For non-randomized controlled studies, we stated we would
1391 use either the Effective Practice and Organisation of Care (EPOC) risk of bias assessment (with domains
1392 for selection bias, performance bias, detection bias, attrition bias, reporting bias, recruitment bias,
1393 baseline characteristics, contamination of intervention, appropriateness of statistical analysis, and

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1394 adjustment for confounding) or the ROBINS-I risk of bias assessment (within domains for confounding,
1395 selection of participants, classification of interventions, deviations from intended interventions, missing
1396 data, measurement of outcomes, and selection of reported results). During the risk of bias assessment,
1397 it became apparent that the domains in the ROBINS-I risk of bias assessment aligned substantially better
1398 to strengths and weaknesses of non-randomized controlled studies; therefore, the ROBINS-I tool was
1399 used throughout the review for such study designs.

1400

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1 Supplementary Tables

2 Supplementary Table 1. Full search strategy

Database	CIDG SR ¹	CENTRAL	LILACS	MEDLINE	EMBASE	CABS Abstract
1	Mosquito*	Mosquito* ti, ab, kw	Mosquito*	Mosquito* mp	Mosquito* mp	Mosquito* mp
2	Anopheles	Anopheles [Mesh]	Anopheles	Anopheles mp, Mesh	Anopheles mp, Emtree	Anopheles mp
3	1 OR 2	1 OR 2	1 OR 2	1 OR 2	1 OR 2	1 OR 2
4	Malaria	Malaria [Mesh]	Malaria	Malaria mp, Mesh	Malaria mp, Emtree	Malaria mp
5	3 AND 4	3 AND 4	3 AND 4	3 AND 4	3 AND 4	3 AND 4
6	Control	Mosquito control [Mesh]	Control	Mosquito control mp, Mesh	Mosquito control mp, Emtree	Mosquito control mp
7	Manag*	Larv* control ti, ab, kw	Manag*	Larv* control mp	Larv* control mp	Larv* control mp
8	6 OR 7	6 OR 7	6 OR 7	Environmental management mp	Environmental management mp	Environmental management mp
9	5 AND 8	5 AND 8	5 AND 8	((Habitat adj 2 modification*) OR modification* OR (habitat adj 2 alteration*) OR alteration* OR landscaping OR drain* OR land reclamation OR land fill OR reclamation ground OR (coverage adj 2 water storage container) OR (coverage adj 2 water surface) OR deforest*) mp	((Habitat adj 2 modification*) OR modification* OR (habitat adj 2 alteration*) OR alteration* OR landscaping OR drain* OR land reclamation OR land fill OR reclamation ground OR (coverage adj 2 water storage container) OR (coverage adj 2 water surface) OR deforest*) mp	((Habitat adj 2 modification*) OR modification* OR (habitat adj 2 alteration*) OR alteration* OR landscaping OR drain* OR land reclamation OR land fill OR reclamation ground OR (coverage adj 2 water storage container) OR (coverage adj 2 water surface) OR deforest*) mp
10				((Habitat adj 2 manipulation*) OR manipulation* OR flushing OR water level OR drain clear* OR shading OR (expos* adj 2 sun) OR sprinkler sanitation OR intermittent irrigation OR vegetation management OR water	((Habitat adj 2 manipulation*) OR manipulation* OR flushing OR water level OR drain clear* OR shading OR (expos* adj 2 sun) OR sprinkler sanitation OR intermittent irrigation OR vegetation management OR water	((Habitat adj 2 manipulation*) OR manipulation* OR flushing OR water level OR drain clear* OR shading OR (expos* adj 2 sun) OR sprinkler sanitation OR intermittent irrigation OR vegetation management OR water

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				management OR alternate wet dry irrigation) mp	management OR alternate wet dry irrigation) mp	management OR alternate wet dry irrigation) mp
11				6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10	6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10	6 OR 7 OR 8 OR 9 OR 10
12				5 AND 11	5 AND 11	5 AND 11

3

4

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5 *Supplementary Table 2. Pre-specified changes for review update from Tusting and colleagues (2013,(8))*

Pre-specified changes for review update	
Protocol section	
Background and research question	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Updating the literature from 2012 – current - Focusing only on habitat modification and habitat manipulation interventions to control malaria
Inclusion criteria	<p>Secondary outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Added density of larvae - Excluded time-infection <p>Types of controls:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Eligible controls will include no intervention or other malaria control interventions covered by a WHO policy recommendation. <p>Type of studies additionally included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Stepped wedge cluster randomised trials (SW-CRT) - Interrupted time series (ITS) studies - Uncontrolled Before-After (BA) studies <p>Study selection:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Including studies with less than one year or one transmission season of baseline data.
Methods	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Additionally, further studies will be identified through other relevant databases and hand searching of grey literature sources. - Where data permit, we will investigate sources of heterogeneity in the meta-analyses using subgroup analyses based on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Different eco- epidemiological settings o Participants o Species of the main vector/s o WHO region

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7 Supplementary table 3. Summary of interventions and eco-epidemiological settings for included studies

Intervention	Study ID	Study design	Details of the intervention	Who was responsible of the intervention	Ecosystem	Vectors	Malaria transmission intensity
Habitat manipulation plus larviciding	Castro 2009 (25)	Controlled before-and-after study	Drains in the city were cleared to increase the water flow and to reduce flooding in the rainy season. Minor repairs such as slab replacement. Larviciding: at the end of the study all sites were treated with larviciding spray	Drain clearance was initially conducted by a contractor with 90% of the workforce local. Intensive education of the local community led to community-led maintenance of drains. Larviciding was organized by the Urban Malaria Control Program	urban	<i>An. gambiae</i> , <i>An. funestus</i>	NI
Habitat manipulation	Imbahale 2011 (29)	Non-randomized controlled trial	1) Shading with local plants. Mosquito larval habitats were created by building a shallow dyke around each habitat. Each of the four locally grown plant species Napier grass (<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i>), arrow root (<i>Maranta arundinacea</i>), papyrus reeds (<i>Cyperus spp.</i>) and rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>) weeded and unweeded 2) Water management with man-made pools, small water canals, paddies.	Centre of Global Health Research (CGHR), KEMRI, Kisian	peri-urban	<i>An. gambiae</i> , <i>An. coustani</i>	high
Habitat manipulation; Habitat manipulation + modification	Imbahale 2012 (28)	Non-randomized controlled trial	1) Shading with arrow root (<i>M. arundinacea</i>) 2) Drainage of canal, land levelling, filling ditches with soil.	NI	rural	<i>An. gambiae</i> , <i>An. arabiensis</i> , <i>An. funestus</i>	NI
Habitat manipulation	Kibret 2018 (21)	Cluster-randomised Controlled Trial	Experimental dam construction (n=12) with three water drawdown treatments and one control (three replicates each). The intervention or	NI	rural	<i>An. arabiensis</i> , <i>An. pharoensis</i>	high

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			no intervention was randomly assigned to the dams: 1) 10 mm.d-1 2) 15 mm.d-1 3) 20 mm.d-1				
Habitat manipulation + modification with larviciding	Lee 2010 (30)	Uncontrolled before-after study	- Prevent importation of malaria: 8 weeks of quarantine on return from malaria endemic countries, screening for foreigners - Early detection of human cases - Mosquito control program <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • shoreline works, drainage, maintenance of drains- clearance vegetation, filling up pools of water • larvicide and adulticide • IRS - Personal protection measures - Malaria contingency plan in case of outbreak	The Singapore Armed Forces (SAF)	rural	<i>An. sundaicus</i> , <i>An. maculates</i>	very low
Habitat manipulation	Munga 2013 (20)	Cluster -randomized controlled trial	Habitats were cleared of grass and water replenishment at different frequency from the local streams: 1) every 10 days (frequent disturbance) 2) every 20 days (intermediate disturbance)	NI	rural	<i>An. gambiae</i> , <i>An. funestus</i> , <i>An. coustani</i> , <i>An. implexus</i>	NI
Habitat manipulation	Mutero 2000 (19)	Cluster-randomized control trial	Three water regimes: 1) flooded before transplanting, drained during transplanting, flooded after transplanting 2) flooded before transplanting, flooded during transplanting, flooded after transplanting 3) flooded before transplanting, drained during transplanting, alternately flooded and drained after transplanting (=intermittent irrigation)	Mwea Irrigation and Agricultural Development (MIAD) experimental station.	rural	<i>An. arabiensis</i>	low
Habitat manipulation	Sahu2014 (27)	Controlled before-after study	Bed dam construction with two sluice gates, opening and closing weekly	Residents of the village-volunteers	rural	<i>An. fluviatilis</i>	high

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Habitat manipulation with larviciding	Samnotra1980 (24)	Controlled before-after study	Encouraged households to eliminate domestic larval habitats alongside larviciding. Control larval habitats like tanks, pitchers, cisterns not treated with larviciding. The attempts were not successful Larviciding: pirimiphos-methyl (sprayed 12.5g active ingredient/ha)	Study staff applied larviciding. Attempts to involve the community for habitat management was not successful	urban	<i>An. culicifacies</i> , <i>An. stephensi</i>	low
Habitat manipulation	Santiago1960 (22)	Controlled before-after study	Automatic siphons were constructed over two streams. Water was flushed to control larvae over distances of 1073m and 2897m downstream, respectively. Existing siphons were repaired.	Local operators within the community and the United States Public Health Service	urban	<i>An. minimus flavirostris</i>	high
Habitat manipulation	Sharma2008 (23)	Controlled before-after study	A small concrete dam construction fitted with three operational gates with sluice iron sheets across the village stream to provide water for irrigation.	Government of India	rural	<i>An. fluviatilis</i> , <i>An. culicifacies</i>	high
Habitat manipulation + modification with larviciding	Shililu2007 (18)	Cluster-Randomised Controlled Trial	Filling or drainage or elimination of rain pools, puddles at water supply points and stream bed pools Larviciding: treatment in rotation with <i>Bti</i> granules, <i>Bs</i> corn granules and temephos	Study staff and local community	rural	<i>An. arabiensis</i> , <i>An. cinereus</i> , <i>An. pretoriensis</i> , <i>An. d'thali</i> , <i>An. funestus</i> , <i>An. squamosus</i> , <i>An. Adenensis</i> , <i>An. demeilloni</i>	NI
Habitat manipulation	Wamae 2010 (17)	Randomised Controlled Trial	Shading drainage channels with Napier Grass planted on both sides of the entire length of the channel. Usual farm activities uninterrupted (occasional cleaning, drainage, land cultivation)	NI	rural	<i>An. gambiae sl</i> , <i>An. funestus</i> , <i>An. coustani</i> , <i>An. rufipes</i> , <i>An. marshalli</i> , <i>An. maculipalpis</i> , <i>An. azaniae</i> , <i>An. implexus</i>	Moderate to high
Habitat manipulation + modification	Yohannes 2005 (26)	Controlled before-and-after study	Filling, draining, shading larval habitats, prohibiting the entry of humans and livestock and filling crossing points of cattle and humans to prevent destruction of plants and creation of larval habitats with hoof-footprints	Local community	rural	<i>An. arabiensis</i> and other <i>anophelines</i>	low

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Supplementary Table 4a.

Summary of findings table for habitat manipulation using water management versus no intervention (Comparison 1a)

Outcome measure	Number of studies (Author, year; individual study overall risk of bias [RoB])	Effect	GRADE criteria					Certainty of evidence
			Risk of bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Inconsistency	Publication bias	
Specific intervention: Floodgate (sluice gates) versus no intervention Co-intervention: Sharma 2008 (23): Routine malaria control activities under the primary health care system included indoor residual spraying (IRS) with DDT from 2001 to 2005 and there was a single round of IRS with a synthetic pyrethroid in 2001, 2003 and 2005. The average house coverage with residual spraying in all the study villages ranged between 60 and 80% during 2001–2005. Sahu 2014 (27): Unclear information report, possibly indoor residual spraying using DDT								
Clinical malaria incidence (children aged 1-5 years)	1 CBA study (Sharma 2008(23); sample size not reported; RoB: serious)	Absolute effect in control group: 1000 events per 1000 children Absolute effect in intervention group: 181.8 events per 1000 children Effect size: A significant reduction was reported between the intervention and control groups (χ^2 test, $p<0.01$).	Serious [#]	Not serious	Very serious [†]	Not serious	Not suspected	Very low ⊕
Malaria parasite prevalence (all ages)	1 CBA study (Sharma 2008(23); 271 participants; RoB: serious)	Absolute effect in control group: Not reported Absolute effect in intervention group: Not reported Effect size: A significant decrease in prevalence in the intervention group (χ^2 test, $p<0.01$), but no significant decline in the control groups (χ^2 test, $p>0.05$).	Serious [#]	Not serious	Very serious [†]	Not serious	Not suspected	Very low ⊕
Density of immature mosquitoes	1 CBA study (Sahu 2014(27); RoB: serious)	Mean density in control group: Downstream: range 0.02 to 0.13 Mean density in intervention group: Downstream: range 0.0 to 0.01 Effect size: A significance decrease in density (t test, $P<0.001$).	Serious [#]	Not serious	Serious [†]	Not serious	Not suspected	Low ⊕⊕

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Outcome measure	Number of studies (Author, year; individual study overall risk of bias [RoB])	Effect	GRADE criteria					Certainty of evidence
			Risk of bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Inconsistency	Publication bias	
Specific intervention: Spillways (using automatic siphons) versus no intervention Co-intervention: No information reported								
Malaria parasite prevalence (children 2-10 years)	1 CBA study (Santiago 1960(22); 866 participants; RoB: very serious)	Absolute effect in control group: 8.6%; Absolute effect in intervention group: 0%; Effect size: RR 0.01, 95% CI 0.00 to 0.16.	Very serious [#]	Not serious	Very serious [†]	Not serious	Not suspected	Very low ⊕
Density of immature mosquitoes	1 CBA study (Santiago 1960(22); RoB: serious)	Mean density in control group: Reduced from 0.70 (SD 0.30) to 0.49 (SD 0.15) Mean density in intervention group: Reduced from 1.40 (SD 0.25) to 0.06 (SD 0.20) Effect size: MD 0.43 (95% CI 0.30 to 0.56)	Serious [#]	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not suspected	Moderate ⊕⊕⊕
Density of adult mosquitoes	1 CBA study (Santiago 1960(22); RoB: serious)	Absolute effect in control group: Increased from 0.30 (SD not estimable) to 0.38 (SD 0.18) Mean density in intervention group: Reduced from 0.40 (SD not estimable) to 0.05 (SD 0.06) Effect size: MD 0.33 (95% CI 0.23 to 0.43)	Serious [#]	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not suspected	Moderate ⊕⊕⊕

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Outcome measure	Number of studies (Author, year; individual study overall risk of bias [RoB])	Effect	GRADE criteria					Certainty of evidence
			Risk of bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Inconsistency	Publication bias	
Specific intervention: Water-level drawdown rates versus no water-level drawdown Co-intervention: No information reported								
Density of immature mosquitoes	1 RCT study (Kibret 2018(21); RoB: some concerns)	Absolute effect in control group: Not reported Absolute effect in intervention groups: Not reported Effect size: 10mm drawdown rate: OR 0.7, P<0.05; 15mm drawdown rate: OR 0.29, P<0.05; 20mm drawdown rate: OR 0.16, P<0.05).	Not serious	Not serious	Serious [†]	Not serious	Not suspected	Moderate ⊕⊕⊕
Specific intervention: Different water regimes versus continuous flooding Co-intervention: None								
Density of immature mosquitoes	1 Cluster-RCT study (Mutero 2000(19); RoB: high)	Absolute density in control groups: Continuous flooding, 425 Absolute density in intervention groups: intermittent irrigation, 4306; drained then flooded, 824; flooded then flooded 775 Effect size: Not estimable	Serious [#]	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not suspected	Moderate ⊕⊕⊕

7 **Key:** # risk of bias is rated as 'serious' due to an overall risk of bias of high for randomised intervention designed studies or serious for non-randomised intervention
8 studies, or 'very serious' due to multiple domains receiving a 'serious' rating for non-randomised intervention studies, † imprecision is rated as 'serious' due to
9 small size of sample, and/or wide confidence intervals or ranges, or 'very serious' due to extremely small size of sample, wide confidence intervals or ranges

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Supplementary Table 4b. Summary of findings table for habitat manipulation using shading versus no intervention (Comparison 1b)

Outcome measure	Number of studies (Author, year; overall risk of bias [RoB])	Effect	GRADE criteria					Certainty of evidence
			Risk of bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Inconsistency	Publication bias	
Specific intervention: Shading habitats with Napier grass versus no intervention Co-intervention: None								
Density of immature mosquitoes	1 RCT study (Wamae 2010(17); RoB: some concerns) & 1 CBA study (Imbahale 2011(29); RoB: serious)	<p>RCT: Mean density in control group: Village 1: 1.61 (SD 0.24); Village 2: 3.82 (SD 0.34) Mean density in intervention group: Village 1: 0.24 (SD 0.08); Village 2: 0.45 (SD 0.09) Effect size: Village 1: 78.4% reduction (ANOVA, P<0.0001); Village 2: 88.0% reduction (ANOVA, P<0.0001)</p> <p>CBA study: Absolute in control group: Not reported Absolute effect in intervention group: Not reported Effect size: Early instars: OR 0.41 (95% CI 0.24 to 0.72); late instars: OR 0.50 (95% CI 0.18 to 1.41)</p>	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not suspected	High ⊕⊕⊕⊕

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Outcome measure	Number of studies (Author, year; overall risk of bias [RoB])	Effect	GRADE criteria					Certainty of evidence
			Risk of bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Inconsistency	Publication bias	
Specific intervention: Shading of water canals with other local plants versus no intervention Co-intervention: None								
Density of immature mosquitoes	1 CBA study (Imbahale 2011(29); RoB: serious)	<p>Absolute effect in control group: Not reported</p> <p>Absolute effect in intervention group: Not reported</p> <p>Effect size:</p> <p>Unweeded rice: Early instars: OR 0.49 (95% CI 0.25 to 0.96); late instars: OR 0.09 (95% CI 0.01 to 0.76);</p> <p>Arrow root: Early instars: OR 0.58 (95% CI 0.33 to 1.00); late instars: OR 0.05 (95% CI 0.01 to 0.38);</p> <p>Water ferns: Early instars: OR 0.29 (95% CI 0.14 to 0.58); late instars: OR 0.26 (95% CI 0.08 to 0.85)</p>	Serious [#]	Not serious	Serious [†]	Not serious	Not suspected	Low ⊕⊕

4 **Key:** # risk of bias is rated a 'serious' due to an overall risk of bias of serious for non-randomised intervention designed studies; † imprecision is rated as 'serious'

5 due to small size of sample and/or wide confidence intervals

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7 *Supplementary Table 4c.* Summary of findings table for habitat manipulation using other/combination management approaches versus no
 8 intervention (Comparison 1c)

Outcome measure	Number of studies (Author, year; overall risk of bias [RoB])	Effect	GRADE criteria					Certainty of evidence
			Risk of bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Inconsistency	Publication bias	
Specific intervention: Frequent and intermediate (disturbance) clearing grass and replenishing water in larval habitats versus no intervention Co-intervention: None								
Density of immature mosquitoes	1 RCT study (Munga 2013(20); RoB: some concerns)	Mean density in control group (no disturbance): 0.118 (SE 0.004) Mean density in intervention group (frequent disturbance): 0.191 (SE 0.006) Mean density in intervention group (intermediate disturbance): 0.155 ±0.005 Effect size: Frequent disturbance: 1.7-fold increase (P<0.001); intermediate disturbance: 1.3-fold increase (P<0.001)	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not suspected	High ⊕⊕⊕⊕

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0 *Supplementary Table 4d.* Summary of findings table for habitat manipulation with larviciding versus no intervention (Comparison 2)

Outcome measure	Number of studies (Author, year; overall risk of bias [RoB])	Effect	GRADE criteria					Certainty of evidence
			Risk of bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Inconsistency	Publication bias	
Specific intervention: Repairing and clearing of drains, cutting grasses, minor repairs (e.g. slab replacement) with larviciding versus no intervention Co-intervention: Indoor residual spraying with DDT.								
Malaria parasite prevalence	1 CBA (Castro 2009(25); 6192 participants; RoB: moderate)	Absolute effect in control group: Not reported Absolute effect in intervention group: Not reported Effect size: Adjusted OR 0.59, 95% CI 0.42 to 0.83	Not serious	Serious ^λ	Serious [†]	Not serious	Not suspected	Low ⊕⊕

1 **Key:** λ indirectness is rated as 'serious' due to directness of intervention where the independent effect of the eligible intervention cannot be assessed due to use
2 of larviciding in the intervention group only; † imprecision is rated as 'serious' due to wide confidence intervals

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5 *Supplementary Table 4e.* Summary of findings table for combination of habitat manipulation and modification versus no intervention (Comparison 3)

Outcome measure	Number of studies (Author, year; overall risk of bias [RoB])	Effect	GRADE criteria					Certainty of evidence
			Risk of bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Inconsistency	Publication bias	
Specific intervention: Construction of drainage canals, planting of papyrus and other reeds for shading versus no intervention Co-intervention: Indoor Residual spraying with DDT used during the pre-intervention phase only								
Density of adult mosquitoes	1 CBA study (Yohannes 2005(26); RoB: serious)	Geometric mean in control group: Reduction from 0.63 to 0.20 Geometric mean in intervention group: Reduction from 4.01 to 0.66 Effect size: 49% relative reduction (95% CI 46.6% to 50%)	Serious [#]	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not suspected	Moderate ⊕⊕⊕
Specific intervention: Drainage of canals, removal of debris, land levelling, and filling of ditches with soil versus no intervention Co-intervention: Roll Back Malaria initiative: insecticide treated nets (ITNs), indoor residual spraying (IRS) and anti-malarial drugs								
Density of immature mosquitoes	1 CBA study (Imbahale 2012(28); RoB: moderate)	Absolute effect in control group: Not reported Absolute effect in intervention group: Not reported Effect size: Village 1: Early instars: OR 0.45 (P<0.05); late instars: OR 0.13 (P<0.05); Village 2: Early instars: OR 0.91 (P>0.05); late instars: OR 0.90 (P<0.05) compared to control habitats, but no effect was seen for early instars (OR 0.91; p>0.05).	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not serious	Not suspected	High ⊕⊕⊕⊕

6 **Key:** # risk of bias is rated a 'serious' due to overall risk of bias rated as 'serious'

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9 *Supplementary Table 4f.* Summary of findings table for combination of habitat manipulation and modification with larviciding versus no intervention
 0 (Comparison 4)

Outcome measure	Number of studies (Author, year; overall risk of bias [RoB])	Effect	GRADE criteria					Certainty of evidence
			Risk of bias	Indirectness	Imprecision	Inconsistency	Publication bias	
Specific intervention: Filling, drainage, or elimination of rain pools and puddles at water supply points or steam bed pools versus no intervention Co-intervention: None; however, insecticide treated nets and indoor residual spraying were conducted as part of the national malaria control program (coverage not stated)								
Density of larval mosquitoes	1 cluster-RCT (Shililu 2007(18); RoB: some concerns)	Mean density in control group: 3.17 (SD 0.11) (one village) Mean density in intervention group: 0.87 (SD 0.04) (one village) Effect size: Not estimable, ANOVA P<0.001 (all villages)	Not serious	Serious ^λ	Not serious	Not serious	Not suspected	Moderate ⊕⊕⊕
Density of adult mosquitoes	1 cluster-RCT (Shililu 2007(18); RoB: some concerns)	Mean in control group: Not reported Mean in intervention group: Not reported Effect size: Not reported, ANOVA P<0.05 (all villages)	Not serious	Serious ^λ	Not serious	Not serious	Not suspected	Moderate ⊕⊕⊕

1 **Key:** λ indirectness is rated as ‘serious’ due to directness of intervention where the independent effect of the eligible intervention cannot be assessed due to
 2 larviciding only being used in the intervention group

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Characteristics of included studies

Castro 2009 (25)

Methods	<p>Study design: Controlled before-and-after study</p> <p>Type of cluster: City</p> <p>Cluster size: 9070 people</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: Intervention arm: four (two habitat manipulation plus short time larviciding-EM, two larviciding-LVC (<i>arm not included</i>)); control arm: two (no intervention plus short time larviciding)-NO</p> <p>Adjusted for clustering? No</p>
Participants	<p>Age: Any</p> <p>Sex: Any</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: Any</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size (Parasite prevalence): 9070 individuals</p> <p>Secondary outcome sample size: NA</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention: Habitat manipulation plus larviciding</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation: Drains in the city were cleared to increase the water flow and to reduce flooding in the rainy season. Minor repairs such as slab replacement.</p> <p>2. Control: no intervention</p> <p>At the end of the study (April 2008- July 2008) all sites were treated with larviciding spray</p> <p>Duration of intervention period: 12 months (EM: 07/2007-03/2008 habitat manipulation only, 04/2008-07/2008 habitat manipulation plus larviciding; LVC: 07/2007-07/2008, larviciding; NO: 07/2007-03/2008 no intervention, 04/2008-07/2008 larviciding. The type and dosage of larviciding used was not specified.</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? Drain clearance was initially conducted by a contractor with 90% of the workforce local. Intensive education of the local community led to community-led maintenance of drains. Larviciding was organized by the Urban Malaria Control Program.</p> <p>Co-interventions: IRS with DDT.</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? Yes</p>
Outcomes	<p>Primary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Malaria parasite prevalence. Six surveys, one every other month <p>Secondary outcome: NA.</p>
Notes	<p>Continent: Africa</p> <p>Country: Tanzania</p> <p>Urban or rural: Urban</p> <p>Transmission intensity: NI</p> <p>Transmission season(s): NI</p>

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	<p>Vectors: <i>An. gambiae</i>, <i>An. funestus</i> Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i> Source of funding: Japan International Cooperation Agency Study included in the previous review: Yes.</p> <p>It is relevant to underline that larviciding was applied in the last four months only in all sites and no data before and after this second intervention was shown. But, the analysis performed by the authors of the paper, was able to capture the positive effect of habitat manipulation alone adjusting for age, rainfall, bed net use, and larviciding spray.</p>	
Risk of bias [Robins-I]		
Outcome assessed	Primary outcome: Parasite prevalence	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Moderate	1.1 Potential for confounding? Yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? Probably yes 1.5 Controlled for confounding domains measured validly and reliably? Probably yes 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? Yes 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders: No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? No 2.2 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? Probably no 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? Probably no
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? No

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		6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? No
Bias in selection of the reported result	Low	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? No 7.3 Different subgroups? No
Overall bias	Moderate	

Imbahale 2011 (29)

Methods	<p>Study design: Non-randomized controlled trial</p> <p>Type of cluster: NA</p> <p>Cluster size: NA</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: NA</p> <p>Adjusted for clustering? NA</p>
Participants	<p>Age: NA</p> <p>Sex: NA</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: NA</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size: NA</p> <p>Secondary outcome sample size (Density) of immature mosquitoes: Not stated</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation:</p> <p>Shading with local plants. Mosquito breeding habitats (1 m × 1 m × 0.5 m) were created by building a shallow dyke (0.2 m) around each habitat. Each of the four locally grown plant species Napier grass (<i>Pennisetum purpureum</i>), arrow root (<i>Maranta arundinacea</i>), papyrus reeds (<i>Cyperus spp.</i>) and rice (<i>Oryza sativa</i>) weeded and unweeded were planted in each habitat and replicated six times. Intervention arm: 30 habitats, control arm: six</p> <p>Control: No intervention, habitats left unplanted</p> <p>Duration of intervention period:</p> <p>1) 13 weeks (03/2007-06/2007)</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? Centre of Global Health Research (CGHR), KEMRI, Kisian</p> <p>Co-interventions: No</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? NA</p>
Outcomes	<p>1. Primary outcome: NA</p>

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	2. Secondary outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of immature mosquitoes. Larvae only (early and late instars). Standard dipping method, max 10 dips/habitat, weekly collection 	
Notes	Continent: Africa Country: Kenya Urban or rural: Peri-urban Transmission intensity: High Transmission season(s): NI Vectors: <i>An. gambiae</i> , <i>An. coustani</i> Malaria parasite: NI Source of funding: Dioraphte Foundation, The Netherlands Study included in the previous review: No	
Risk of bias [Robins-I]		
Outcome assessed	Secondary outcome: Density of immature mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Serious	1.1 Potential for confounding? Yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? No 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? Probably no 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? No 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Probably yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? Probably no 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? Probably no

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Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? Probably no 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? No
Bias in selection of the reported result	Moderate	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? Yes 7.3 Different subgroups? No
Overall bias	Serious	

Imbahale 2012 (28)

Methods	<p>Study design: Non-randomized controlled trial</p> <p>Type of cluster: Village</p> <p>Cluster size: NI</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: Intervention arm: 1 in each of the two villages; control arm: 1 in each of the two villages</p> <p>Adjusted for clustering? No</p>
Participants	<p>Age: NA</p> <p>Sex: NA</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: NA</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size: NA</p> <p>Secondary outcome sample size (Density of immature mosquitoes): Not stated</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation: Shading with arrow root (<i>M. arundinacea</i>)</p> <p>2. Habitat manipulation + modification: Drainage of canal (land levelling, filling ditches with soil). Only data on drainage was reported.</p> <p>3. Control: no intervention</p> <p>Duration of intervention period:</p> <p>1) Fort Ternan village: 8 months (08/2008-03/2009), Lunyerere village: 12 months (04/2008-03/2009)</p> <p>2) Lunyerere village: 12 months (04/2008-03/2009)</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? NI</p> <p>Co-interventions: Roll Back Malaria initiative: insecticide treated nets (ITNs), indoor residual spraying (IRS) and anti-malarial drugs</p>

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	Co-interventions equal in each arm? Yes	
Outcomes	1.Primary outcome: NA 2.Secondary outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of immature mosquitoes. Larvae only (early and late instars). Standard dipping method. Data collected once a week but reported in the paper monthly, average larvae/dip 	
Notes	Continent: Africa Country: Kenya Urban or rural: Rural Transmission intensity: NI Transmission season(s): NI Vectors: <i>An. gambiae</i> , <i>An. arabiensis</i> , <i>An. funestus</i> Malaria parasite: NI Source of funding: NI Study included in the previous review: No	
Risk of bias [Robins-I]		
Outcome assessed	Secondary outcome: Density of immature mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Low	1.1 Potential for confounding? Probably no 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? No 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? No 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? No
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes

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		5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? NProbably n 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? No
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? Probably no 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? No
Bias in selection of the reported result	Moderate	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? Yes 7.3 Different subgroups? Probably no
Overall bias	Moderate	

Kibret 2018 (21)

Methods	Study design: Cluster Randomised Controlled Trial Type of cluster: Dam site Cluster size: NA Number of clusters in each arm: 3 Adjusted for clustering? No
Participants	Age: NA Sex: NA Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: NA Primary outcome sample size: NA Secondary outcome sample size (Density of immature mosquitoes): Not stated
Interventions	Intervention: Details of the intervention: 1. Habitat manipulation: Three water drawdown treatments and one control (three replicates each): 1) 10 mm.d-1 2) 15 mm.d-1 3) 20 mm.d-1 4) no water-level drawdown (control group) Duration of intervention period: 12 weeks (10/2013-11/2013 main season, 02/2014-03/2014 dry season) Who was responsible for LSM? NI Co-interventions: NI

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	Co-interventions equal in each arm? NI	
Outcomes	1.Primary outcome: NA 2.Secondary outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of immature mosquitoes Larvae only. Standard dipping method. Weekly sampling. 	
Notes	Continent: Africa Country: Ethiopia Urban or rural: Rural Transmission intensity: High Transmission season(s): October-November Vectors: <i>An. arabiensis</i> , <i>An. pharoensis</i> Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i> , <i>Pl. vivax</i> Source of funding: International Foundation for Science and University of New England Study included in the previous review: No	
Risk of bias [RoB2]		
Outcome assessed	Secondary outcome: Density of immature mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to randomization process	Some concerns	1.1 Allocation sequence random: Probably yes 1.2 Allocation sequence concealed: Probably no 1.3 Baseline differences between groups: Probably no
Bias arising from the timing and identification and recruitment of individual participants in relation to timing of randomization	Low	1b.1 All participants identified before randomisation of clusters: Probably yes 1b.3 Baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification/recruitment of individual participants between arms: Probably no
Bias due to deviations from the intended interventions (effect of assignment to intervention)	Low	2.1a Participants aware they were in a trial: Probably no 2.2 People delivering intervention were aware of assignment during the trial: Yes 2.3 Deviations from intended intervention: Probably no 2.5a Were any clusters analysed in a group different from the one which assigned: Probably no

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		2.5b Where any participants analysed in a group different from assigned cluster: Probably no
Bias due to missing outcome data	Low	3.1a Data available for all, or nearly all, clusters: Yes 3.1b Data available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters: Yes
Bias due to measurement of the outcome	Low	4.1a Outcome assessors aware that trial was taking place: Yes 4.1b Outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by participants: Yes 4.2 Assessment of outcome likely to be influenced by knowledge of intervention received: Probably no
Bias due to selection of the reported result	Low	5.1 Numerical result likely to be selected based on multiple outcome measurements: Probably no 5.2 Numerical results likely to be selected based on multiple eligible analyses: Probably no
Overall bias	Some concerns	

Lee 2010 (30)

Methods	<p>Study design: Uncontrolled before-after study</p> <p>Type of cluster: Island</p> <p>Cluster size: Unclear</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: Intervention arm: one; control arm: no</p> <p>Adjusted for clustering? NA</p>
Participants	<p>Age: Any</p> <p>Sex: Any</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: NI</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size: NA</p> <p>Secondary outcome sample size (Density of adult mosquitoes): Not stated</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1.Habitat manipulation + modification + larviciding</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prevent importation of malaria: 8 weeks of quarantine on return from malaria endemic countries, screening for foreigners - Early detection of human cases -Mosquito control program • habitat manipulation + modification: shoreline works, drainage, maintenance of drains-clearance vegetation, filling up pools of water

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • larvicide and adulticide • IRS <p>- Personal protection measures - Malaria contingency plan in case of outbreak</p> <p>2.Control: NA</p> <p>Duration of intervention period: 24 months (12/2006-12/2008)</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? The Singapore Armed Forces (SAF)</p> <p>Co-interventions: No</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? NA</p>	
Outcomes	<p>1.Primary outcome: NA</p> <p>2.Secondary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Density of adult mosquitoes. Human landing catch. Weekly (11/2006-04/2007), then fortnightly (05/2007-12/2008) 	
Notes	<p>Continent: Asia</p> <p>Country: Japan</p> <p>Urban or rural: Rural</p> <p>Transmission intensity: Very low</p> <p>Transmission season(s): NI</p> <p>Vectors: <i>An. sundaicus</i>, <i>An. maculates</i></p> <p>Malaria parasite: NI</p> <p>Source of funding: The Singapore Armed Forces (SAF)</p> <p>Study included in the previous review: No</p>	
Risk of bias [No Tool used]		
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Overall bias	Critical	Study design: uncontrolled before-after study

Munga 2013 (20)

Methods	<p>Study design: Cluster randomized controlled trial</p> <p>Type of cluster: Habitats area</p> <p>Cluster size: NA</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: 10</p> <p>Adjusted for clustering? No</p>	
Participants	<p>Age: NA</p> <p>Sex: NA</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: NA</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size: NA</p> <p>Secondary outcome sample size (Density of immature mosquitoes): Not stated</p>	
Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation: Habitats were cleared of grass and water replenishment at different frequency:</p>	

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	<p>1) habitats were cleared of grass and water was replenished from the local stream every 10 days (frequent disturbance)</p> <p>2) habitats were cleared of grass and water was replenished from the local stream every 20 days (intermediate disturbance)</p> <p>2. Control: no intervention (no disturbance for 30 days)</p> <p>Duration of intervention period: 6 months (09/2005-02/2006). This experiment was conducted in one month (30 days) after which the no-disturbance habitats were also cleared of water and grass and the experiment repeated again.</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? NI</p> <p>Co-interventions: no</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? NA</p>	
Outcomes	<p>1.Primary outcome: NA</p> <p>2.Secondary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of immature mosquitoes. Larvae only. Standard dipping method, 50 dips per habitat. Daily collection. 	
Notes	<p>Continent: Africa</p> <p>Country: Kenya</p> <p>Urban or rural: Rural</p> <p>Transmission intensity: NI</p> <p>Transmission season(s): NI</p> <p>Vectors: <i>An. gambiae</i>, <i>An. funestus</i>, <i>An. coustani</i>, <i>An. implexus</i></p> <p>Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i></p> <p>Source of funding: WHO/UNDP/WORLD BANK Special Programme for Research and Training in Tropical Diseases (TDR)</p> <p>Study included in the previous review: No</p>	
Risk of bias [RoB2]		
Outcome assessed	Secondary outcome: density of immature mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to randomization process	Some concerns	<p>1.1 Allocation sequence random: Probably yes</p> <p>1.2 Allocation sequence concealed: Probably no</p> <p>1.3 Baseline differences between groups: Probably no</p>
Bias arising from the timing and identification and recruitment of individual participants in relation to timing of randomization	Low	<p>1b.1 All participants identified before randomisation of clusters: Probably yes</p> <p>1b.3 Baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification/recruitment of individual participants between arms: Probably no</p>

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Bias due to deviations from the intended interventions (effect of assignment to intervention)	Low	2.1a Participants aware they were in a trial: Probably no 2.2 People delivering intervention were aware of assignment during the trial: Yes 2.3 Deviations from intended intervention: Probably no 2.5a Were any clusters analysed in a group different from the one which assigned: Probably no 2.5b Where any participants analysed in a group different from assigned cluster: Probably no
Bias due to missing outcome data	Low	3.1a Data available for all, or nearly all, clusters: Yes 3.1b Data available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters: Yes
Bias due to measurement of the outcome	Low	4.1a Outcome assessors aware that trial was taking place: Yes 4.1b Outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by participants: Yes 4.2 Assessment of outcome likely to be influenced by knowledge of intervention received: No
Bias due to selection of the reported result	Low	5.1 Numerical result likely to be selected based on multiple outcome measurements: Probably no 5.2 Numerical results likely to be selected based on multiple eligible analyses: Probably no
Overall bias	Some concerns	

Mutero 2000 (19)

Methods	Study design: Cluster Randomized controlled trial Type of cluster: Experimental plot Cluster size: NA Number of clusters in each arm: 4 Adjusted for clustering? No
Participants	Age: NA Sex: NA Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: NA Primary outcome sample size: NA

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	Secondary outcome sample size (Density of immature mosquitoes): Not stated	
Interventions	<p>Intervention: Details of the intervention: 1.Habitat manipulation: 1) flooded before transplanting, drained during transplanting, flooded after transplanting 2) flooded before transplanting, flooded during transplanting, flooded after transplanting 3) flooded before transplanting, drained during transplanting, alternately flooded and drained after transplanting (=intermittent irrigation) 2. Control: continuously flooded without rice cultivation Duration of intervention period: 12 weeks (07/09/1998-24/11/1998) Who was responsible for LSM? Mwea Irrigation and Agricultural Development (MIAD) experimental station. Co-interventions: No Co-interventions equal in each arm? NA</p>	
Outcomes	<p>1.Primary outcome: NA 2.Secondary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of immature mosquitoes). Larvae only. Standard dipping method. The sampling unit was 350 ml of water, 20 samples for each subplot and then larvae were pooled. Sampling on two occasions prior to transplanting of rice seedlings then, twice/week. 	
Notes	<p>Continent: Africa Country: Kenya Urban or rural: Rural Transmission intensity: Low Transmission season(s): NI Vectors: <i>An. arabiensis</i> Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i> Source of funding: NI Study included in the previous review: No</p>	
Risk of bias [RoB2]		
Outcome assessed		
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to randomization process	Some concerns	1a.1 Allocation sequence random: Yes 1a.2 Allocation sequence concealed: Probably no 1a.3 Baseline differences between groups: Probably no
Bias arising from the timing and	Low	1b.1 All participants identified before randomisation of clusters: Yes

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identification and recruitment of individual participants in relation to timing of randomization		1b.3 Baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification/recruitment of individual participants between arms: Probably no
Bias due to deviations from the intended interventions (effect of assignment to intervention)	High	2.1a Participants aware they were in a trial: Probably no 2.1b Participants aware of assigned intervention: Probably yes 2.2 People delivering intervention were aware of assignment during the trial: Yes 2.3 Deviations from intended intervention: Probably no 2.5a Were any clusters analysed in a group different from the one which assigned: Probably no 2.5b Where any participants analysed in a group different from assigned cluster: Probably no
Bias due to missing outcome data	Low	3.1a Data available for all, or nearly all, clusters: Yes 3.1b Data available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters: Yes
Bias due to measurement of the outcome	Low	4.1a Outcome assessors aware that trial was taking place: Yes 4.1b Outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by participants: Yes 4.2 Assessment of outcome likely to be influenced by knowledge of intervention received: Probably no
Bias due to selection of the reported result	Low	5.1 Numerical result likely to be selected based on multiple outcome measurements: Probably no 5.2 Numerical results likely to be selected based on multiple eligible analyses: Probably no
Overall bias	High	

Sahu 2014 (27)

Methods	Study design: Controlled before-after study Type of cluster: Village Cluster size: NI
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	Number of clusters in each arm: Intervention arm: one; control arm: one Adjusted for clustering? NA	
Participants	Age: NA Sex: NA Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: NA Primary outcome sample size: NA Secondary outcome sample size (Density of immature mosquitoes): Not stated	
Interventions	Intervention: Details of the intervention: 1. Habitat manipulation: Two sluice gates on bed-dam, opening and closing weekly 2. Control: No intervention. No sluice gates on bed-dam Duration of intervention period: four months (06/2010-09/2010) Who was responsible for LSM? Residents of the village-volunteers Co-interventions: unclear (probably IRS using DDT) Co-interventions equal in each arm? Unclear	
Outcomes	1. Primary outcome: NA 2. Secondary outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of immature mosquitoes. Larvae and /or pupae. Dipping method. Data collected fortnightly (prior to the construction of bed-dam), or weekly (after to the construction of bed-dam) 	
Notes	Continent: Asia Country: India Urban or rural: Rural Transmission intensity: High Transmission season(s): Winter and early summer Vectors: <i>An. fluviatilis</i> Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i> Source of funding: unclear (District administration, Koraput) Study included in the previous review: No	
Risk of bias [Robins-I]		
Outcome assessed	Secondary outcome: Density immature mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Serious	1.1 Potential for confounding? Yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? No 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No

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Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? Probably no 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Probably yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? No 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? No
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? Probably no 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? Probably no
Bias in selection of the reported result	Moderate	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? Probably yes 7.3 Different subgroups? Probably no
Overall bias	Serious	

Samnotra 1980 (24)

Methods	Study design: Controlled before-after study Type of cluster: town Cluster size: intervention arm 92000 individuals, control arm 5000 individuals Number of clusters in each arm: Intervention arm: one; control arm: one Adjusted for clustering? NA
Participants	Age: Any

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	<p>Sex: Any</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: Any</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical malaria incidence: intervention arm 92000 individuals, control arm 5000 individuals • Malaria parasite prevalence: unclear <p>Secondary outcome sample size:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Density of immature mosquitoes: Not stated • Density of adult mosquitoes: Not stated
Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation + larviciding: encouraged households to eliminate domestic larval habitats alongside larviciding. Control breeding sites like tanks, pitchers, cisterns not treated with larviciding. The attempts were not successful. Pirimiphos-methyl (sprayed 12.5g active ingredient/ha)</p> <p>2. Control: no intervention</p> <p>Duration of intervention period: 16 months (08/1976-11/1977)</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? Study staff applied larviciding. Attempts to involve the community for habitat management was not successful</p> <p>Co-interventions: case management and treatment for fever cases</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? yes</p>
Outcomes	<p>1. Primary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical malaria incidence. Continuous community surveillance • Parasite prevalence. Selected community surveys <p>2. Secondary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Density of immature mosquitoes. Larvae and pupae. Dipping method. Five dips made with standard size ladle, and the average number of 3rd and 4th instar larvae, and also pupae, recorded. 100 larval sites, 20 each day. • Density of adult mosquitoes. 80 catching stations indoor. Adults collected with aspirators.
Notes	<p>Continent: Asia</p> <p>Country: India</p> <p>Urban or rural: Urban</p> <p>Transmission intensity: Low</p> <p>Transmission season(s): NI</p> <p>Vectors: <i>An. culicifacies</i>, <i>An. stephensi</i></p> <p>Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i></p> <p>Source of funding: Haryana State Health Authorities, Alkali and Chemical Corporation of India Ltd, ICI Plant Protection Division</p> <p>Study included in the previous review: Yes.</p>

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	Given the information provided in the text on the failure in the attempt of performing habitat manipulation by the community, the results of the intervention should be totally addressed to larviciding. So, we considered it appropriate not to extract data in this review. The previous review reported the results as an integrated intervention.	
Risk of bias [Robins-I]		
Outcome assessed	Primary outcome: Clinical malaria incidence (due to critical risk of bias regarding study design, the Risk of bias for other outcome measures have not been provided)	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Critical	1.1 Potential for confounding? Yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? No 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables: No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? Probably no 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Probably yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Moderate	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Probably no 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Probably yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Critical	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? Yes 4.2 Deviations unbalanced between groups and likely to affect the outcome? Yes
Bias due to missing data	Moderate	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably no 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? No information 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? No information 5.4 Proportion of missing data similar across interventions? No information 5.5 Evidence that results were robust to missing data? Probably no
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? Probably no

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		6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? Probably no
Bias in selection of the reported result	Low	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? Probably no 7.2 Multiple analyses? No information 7.3 Different subgroups? Probably no
Overall bias	Critical	

Santiago 1960 (22)

Methods	<p>Study design: Controlled before-after study</p> <p>Type of cluster: area of the city</p> <p>Cluster size: Population of the city 25545. Population in the control and intervention areas unclear</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: Intervention arm: one; control arm: one</p> <p>Adjusted for clustering? NA</p>
Participants	<p>Age: Two to ten years, infants <1 year</p> <p>Sex: Any</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: Any</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size (Malaria parasite prevalence): Children 2-10 years old only. Intervention area: pre-intervention 646, post-intervention: 566. Control area: pre-intervention 210, 277; post-intervention 280</p> <p>Secondary outcome sample size:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Density of immature mosquitoes: Not stated • Density of adult mosquitoes: Not stated • Entomological inoculation rate (EIR): Intervention area: pre-intervention 168, 175; post-intervention: 222. Control area: pre-intervention 63,52; post-intervention 83
Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation: Spillways (automatic siphons) were constructed over two streams which were the main larval habitats. Water was flushed to control larvae over distances of 1073m and 2897m downstream, respectively. Existing siphons were repaired</p> <p>4.Control: No flushing</p>

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	<p>Duration of intervention period: 16 months (07/1953, 10/1954)</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? Local operators within the community and the United Stated Public Health Service</p> <p>Co-interventions: NI</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? NA</p>	
Outcomes	<p>1.Primary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Malaria parasite prevalence. Community based surveys <p>2.Secondary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of immature mosquitoes: Larvae only. Dipping method. Mean density of larvae per dip were reported. Collection fortnightly, 6 months before – 16 months during flushing. Density of adult mosquitoes. Adults were collected with: 1. Carabao-baited traps 2.per-hour trapping-human baited trap. Mean density of adult mosquitoes per month were recorded. Collection fortnightly 6 months before – 16 months during flushing. Entomological inoculation rate (EIR): infant only. One time/year data collection. No data on the method used for EIR calculation 	
Notes	<p>Continent: Asia</p> <p>Country: Philippine</p> <p>Urban or rural: urban</p> <p>Transmission intensity: high</p> <p>Transmission season(s): NI</p> <p>Vectors: <i>An. minimus flavirostris</i></p> <p>Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i></p> <p>Source of funding: Malaria Eradication Project, San Pablo City</p> <p>Study included in the previous review: yes.</p> <p>The duration of the study is 16 months and not 12 as reported in the previous review[3], being the duration of the continuous flushing equal to 16 months</p>	
Risk of bias [Robins-I]		
Outcome assessed	Primary outcome: Malaria parasite prevalence	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Serious	<p>1.1 Potential for confounding? Probably yes</p> <p>1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding: No</p> <p>1.6 Control for post-intervention variables: No</p> <p>1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders: No</p>
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	<p>2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? Probably no</p> <p>2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Probably yes</p>

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Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Serious	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably no 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? Probably no 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? Probably no 5.4 Proportion of missing data similar across interventions? Probably no 5.5 Evidence that results were robust to missing data? Probably no
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? Probably no 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? Probably no
Bias in selection of the reported result	Low	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? No 7.3 Different subgroups? No
Overall bias	Serious	
Outcome assessed	Primary outcome: Density of immature mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Serious	1.1 Potential for confounding? Probably yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? Probably no 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No

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Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? Probably no 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Probably yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? No 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? No 5.4 Proportion of missing data similar across interventions? Probably yes
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? Probably no 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? Probably no
Bias in selection of the reported result	Low	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? No 7.3 Different subgroups? No
Overall bias	Serious	
Outcome assessed	Primary outcome: Density of adult mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement

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Bias due to confounding	Serious	1.1 Potential for confounding? Probably yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? Probably no 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? Probably no 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Probably yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? No 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? No 5.4 Proportion of missing data similar across interventions? Probably yes
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? Probably no 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? Probably no
Bias in selection of the reported result	Low	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? No 7.3 Different subgroups? No

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Overall bias	Serious	
Outcome assessed	Primary outcome: Entomological inoculation rate (EIR)	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Serious	1.1 Potential for confounding? Probably yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? No 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? Probably no 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Probably yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Serious	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably no 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? Probably no 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? Probably no 5.4 Proportion of missing data similar across interventions? Probably no 5.5 Evidence that results were robust to missing data? Probably no
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? Probably no 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? Probably no

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Bias in selection of the reported result	Low	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? No 7.3 Different subgroups? No
Overall bias	Serious	

Sharma 2008 (23)

Methods	<p>Study design: Controlled before-after study</p> <p>Type of cluster: Village</p> <p>Cluster size: Intervention arm: 271 individuals; control arm: 143 and 156 individuals. Total: 570</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: Intervention arm: one; control arm: two</p> <p>Adjusted for clustering? No</p>
Participants	<p>Age: Any</p> <p>Sex: Any</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: Any</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical malaria incidence: 570 individuals • Parasite prevalence: 40% of households /village were randomly selected <p>Secondary outcome sample size: NA</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation: Floodgates comprising of three operational gates fitted with sluice iron sheets at a height of 4m from ground level on a constructed small dam (concrete dam of 25m length and 4m height) across the stream in the village to provide water for irrigation. Sluice gates may be opened during the rainy season for discharge of excess water.</p> <p>2. Control: No intervention</p> <p>Duration of intervention period: 16 months (09/2002-12/2003)</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? Government of India</p> <p>Co-interventions: Routine malaria control activities under the primary health care system included indoor residual spraying with DDT from 2001 to 2005 and there was a single round of indoor residual spraying with a synthetic pyrethroid in 2001, 2003 and 2005. The average house coverage with residual spraying in all the study villages ranged between 60 and 80% during 2001–2005.</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? Yes</p>
Outcomes	<p>1. Primary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical malaria incidence: Active and passive surveillance. Trained workers (1 per village) were going house by house once a week and tested people found to have

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	<p>an axillary temperature of >37.5 °C or a history of fever in the previous 48 h. Blood smears test</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Parasite prevalence: Three cross-sectional surveys each year 2001–2005 in March, June and November (intermediate), low and high malaria transmission seasons. Microscopic examination. <p>2.Secondary outcome: NA</p>	
Notes	<p>Continent: Asia Country: India Urban or rural: Rural Transmission intensity: High Transmission season(s): Perennial transmission throughout the year but peaks during the post-monsoon months of October to December. Malaria transmission season: March (intermediate), June (low) and November (high) Vectors: <i>An. fluviatilis</i>, <i>An. culicifacies</i> Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i> Source of funding: Integrated Disease Vector Control Project being funded by the Indian Council of Medical Research (ICMR) and Ministry of Health and Family Welfare, Government of India. Study included in the previous review: Yes. The duration of the intervention in the previous review[3] was calculated as 23 months.</p>	
Risk of bias [Robins-I]		
Outcome assessed	Primary outcome: Clinical malaria incidence	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Serious	1.1 Potential for confounding? Yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? No 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? No 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no

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Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? Probably no 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? Probably no
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? No 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? No
Bias in selection of the reported result	Moderate	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? Probably yes 7.3 Different subgroups? No
Overall bias	Serious	
Outcome assessed	Primary outcome: Parasite Prevalence	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Serious	1.1 Potential for confounding? Probably yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? No 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? No 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes

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		3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? Probably no
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? Probably no 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? Probably no
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? No 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? No
Bias in selection of the reported result	Moderate	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? Probably yes 7.3 Different subgroups? No
Overall bias	Serious	

Shililu 2007 (18)

Methods	<p>Study design: Cluster-Randomised Controlled Trial</p> <p>Type of cluster: Village</p> <p>Cluster size: NA</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: 4</p> <p>Adjusted for clustering? No</p>
Participants	<p>Age: NA</p> <p>Sex: NA</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: NA</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size: NA</p> <p>Secondary outcome sample size:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Density of immature mosquitoes: not stated • Density of adult mosquitoes: not stated

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Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation + modification + larviciding: Filling or drainage or elimination of rain pools, puddles at water supply points and stream bed pools. Treatment in rotation with <i>Bti</i> granules, <i>Bs</i> corn granules and temephos</p> <p>2. Control: No intervention</p> <p>Duration of intervention period: 24 months (no dates specified)</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? Study staff and local community</p> <p>Co-interventions: None. However, ITNs and IRS were conducted as part of the national malaria control program (coverage not stated)</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? NI</p>	
Outcomes	<p>1.Primary outcome: NA</p> <p>2.Secondary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Density of immature mosquitoes. Larvae only. Standard dipping techniques and 10–20 dips taken in each larval habitat. Larval densities were expressed as number of larvae per 10 dips because the number of larvae was low Density of adult mosquitoes: CDC miniature light traps from dusk to dawn (12 hours), 2 consecutive days/wk, 6 in each village, indoor outdoor light traps. <i>An. arabiensis</i> density is expressed as number of mosquitoes per light trap. 	
Notes	<p>Continent: Africa</p> <p>Country: Eritrea</p> <p>Urban or rural: Rural</p> <p>Transmission intensity: NI</p> <p>Transmission season(s): Short period of transmission coinciding with short rainy season</p> <p>Vectors: <i>An. arabiensis</i>, <i>An. cinereus</i>, <i>An. pretoriensis</i>, <i>An. d'thali</i>, <i>An. funestus</i>, <i>An. squamosus</i>, <i>An Adenensis</i>, <i>An. demeilloni</i></p> <p>Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i></p> <p>Source of funding: United States Agency for International Development, Environmental Health Project, International Center of Insect Physiology and Ecology, National Institutes of Health</p> <p>Study included in the previous review: Yes</p>	
Risk of bias [RoB2]		
Outcome assessed	Secondary outcome: Density of immature mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to randomization process	Some concerns	1a.1 Allocation sequence random: Probably yes 1a.2 Allocation sequence concealed: Probably no 1a.3 Baseline differences between groups: Probably no

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Bias arising from the timing and identification and recruitment of individual participants in relation to timing of randomization	Low	1b.1 All participants identified before randomisation of clusters: Probably yes 1b.3 Baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification/recruitment of individual participants between arms: Probably no
Bias due to deviations from the intended interventions (effect of assignment to intervention)	Low	2.1a Participants aware they were in a trial: Probably no 2.2 People delivering intervention were aware of assignment during the trial: Yes 2.3 Deviations from intended intervention: Probably no 2.5a Were any clusters analysed in a group different from the one which assigned: Probably no 2.5b Where any participants analysed in a group different from assigned cluster: Probably no
Bias due to missing outcome data	Low	3.1a Data available for all, or nearly all, clusters: Yes 3.1b Data available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters: Yes
Bias due to measurement of the outcome	Low	4.1a Outcome assessors aware that trial was taking place: Yes 4.1b Outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by participants: Yes 4.2 Assessment of outcome likely to be influenced by knowledge of intervention received: Probably no
Bias due to selection of the reported result	Low	5.1 Numerical result likely to be selected based on multiple outcome measurements: Probably no 5.2 Numerical results likely to be selected based on multiple eligible analyses: Probably no
Overall bias	Some concerns	
Outcome assessed	Secondary outcome: Density of adult mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement

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Bias due to randomization process	Some concerns	1a.1 Allocation sequence random: Probably yes 1a.2 Allocation sequence concealed: Probably no 1a.3 Baseline differences between groups: Probably no
Bias arising from the timing and identification and recruitment of individual participants in relation to timing of randomization	Low	1b.1 All participants identified before randomisation of clusters: Probably yes 1b.3 Baseline imbalances that suggest differential identification/recruitment of individual participants between arms: Probably no
Bias due to deviations from the intended interventions (effect of assignment to intervention)	Low	2.1a Participants aware they were in a trial: Probably no 2.2 People delivering intervention were aware of assignment during the trial: Yes 2.3 Deviations from intended intervention: Probably no 2.5a Were any clusters analysed in a group different from the one which assigned: Probably no 2.5b Where any participants analysed in a group different from assigned cluster: Probably no
Bias due to missing outcome data	Low	3.1a Data available for all, or nearly all, clusters: Yes 3.1b Data available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters: Yes
Bias due to measurement of the outcome	Low	4.1a Outcome assessors aware that trial was taking place: Yes 4.1b Outcome assessors aware of the intervention received by participants: Yes 4.2 Assessment of outcome likely to be influenced by knowledge of intervention received: Probably no
Bias due to selection of the reported result	Low	5.1 Numerical result likely to be selected based on multiple outcome measurements: Probably no 5.2 Numerical results likely to be selected based on multiple eligible analyses: Probably no

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Overall bias	Some concerns	
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Wamae 2010 (17)

Methods	<p>Study design: Randomised Controlled Trial</p> <p>Type of cluster: NA</p> <p>Cluster size: NA</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: N/A</p> <p>Adjusted for clustering? N/A</p>
Participants	<p>Age: NA</p> <p>Sex: NA</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: NA</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size: NA</p> <p>Secondary outcome sample size (Density of immature mosquitoes): not stated</p>
Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation: Shading drainage channels (n= 11, 6 in Lunyerere and 5 in Emutete village) with Napier Grass planted on both sides of the entire length of the channel. Usual farm activities uninterrupted (occasional cleaning, drainage, land cultivation). Channels were randomly designated to intervention and control.</p> <p>2. Control: no shaded channels (n= 11, 6 in Lunyerere and 5 in Emutete village)</p> <p>Duration of intervention period: Lunyerere 10 months (11/2006-08/2007), Emutete 8 months (01/2007-08/2007)</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? NI</p> <p>Co-interventions: No</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? NA</p>
Outcomes	<p>1.Primary outcome: NA</p> <p>2.Secondary outcome: Density of immature mosquitoes. Larvae only. Standard dipping method, collection once every week. The mean number (density) of <i>An. gambiae</i> larvae.</p>
Notes	<p>Continent: Africa</p> <p>Country: Kenya</p> <p>Urban or rural: Rural</p> <p>Transmission intensity: Moderate to high. (In the study area: 20-44.3% school aged children)</p> <p>Transmission season(s): NI</p> <p>Vectors: <i>An. gambiae sl</i>, <i>An. funestus</i>, <i>An. coustani</i>, <i>An. rufipes</i>, <i>An. marshalli</i>, <i>An. maculipalpis</i>, <i>An. azaniae</i>, <i>An. implexus</i></p> <p>Malaria parasite: NI</p> <p>Source of funding: Dioraphte Foundation, The Netherlands</p> <p>Study included in the previous review: No</p>
Risk of bias [RoB2]	
Outcome assessed	Secondary outcome: Density of immature mosquitoes

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Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to randomization process	Some concerns	1.1 Allocation sequence random: Probably yes 1.2 Allocation sequence concealed: Probably no 1.3 Baseline differences between groups: Probably no
Bias due to deviations from the intended interventions (effect of assignment to intervention)	Low	2.1 Participants aware of their assigned intervention during the trial: Probably yes 2.2 People delivering intervention were aware of assignment during the trial: Yes 2.3 Deviations from intended intervention: Probably no 2.6 Appropriate analysis used to estimate the effect of assignment to intervention: Yes
Bias due to missing outcome data	Low	3.1 Data available for all, or nearly all, participants within clusters: Probably yes
Bias due to measurement of the outcome	Low	4.1 Method of measuring outcome inappropriate: No 4.2 Measurement or ascertainment of outcome have differed between intervention groups: No 4.3 Outcome assessors aware of intervention received: Yes 4.4 Assessment of outcome likely to be influenced by knowledge of intervention received: Probably no
Bias due to selection of the reported result	Some concerns	5.1 Results analysed in accordance with pre-specified analysis plan: No 5.2 Numerical result likely to be selected based on multiple outcome measurements: Probably yes 5.3 Numerical results likely to be selected based on multiple eligible analyses: Probably no
Overall bias	Some concerns	

Yohannes 2005 (26)

Methods	<p>Study design: Controlled before-and-after study</p> <p>Type of cluster: Village</p> <p>Cluster size: intervention village: 372, control village: 1237</p> <p>Number of clusters in each arm: Intervention arm: one; control arm: one</p>
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	Adjusted for clustering? No
Participants	<p>Age: children <10 years</p> <p>Sex: Any</p> <p>Co-morbidities and/or pregnancy: Any</p> <p>Primary outcome sample size</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical malaria incidence: all children <10 years in the two villages. Intervention village: 86, control village: 322 • Malaria parasite prevalence: all children <10 years in the two villages. Intervention village: 86, control village: 322 <p>Secondary outcome sample size:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Density of immature mosquitoes: Not stated • Density of adult mosquitoes: Not stated
Interventions	<p>Intervention:</p> <p>Details of the intervention:</p> <p>1. Habitat manipulation + modification: Filling, draining, shading breeding sites, prohibiting the entry of humans and livestock and filling crossing points of cattle and humans to prevent destruction of plants and creation of breeding sites with hoof-footprints</p> <p>2. Control: No intervention</p> <p>Duration of intervention period: 11 months (02/2000-12/2000)</p> <p>Who was responsible for LSM? Local community</p> <p>Co-interventions: IRS with DDT used during the pre-intervention only</p> <p>Co-interventions equal in each arm? Yes</p>
Outcomes	<p>1. Primary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical malaria incidence: rate of cases per 100 child months at risk. One sample in the dry and one in the wet season. In the paper, author stated that there were too low number of cases to report results and perform analysis (risk of bias not performed) • Malaria parasite prevalence: malaria prevalence rate. Data on prevalence in pre-intervention only. One sample in the dry and one in the wet season. In the paper, author stated that there were too low number of cases to report results and perform analysis (risk of bias not performed) <p>2. Secondary outcome:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Density of immature mosquitoes: Standard dipping method. Collection twice monthly. Up to 10 dips were made in each type of water body. • Density of adult mosquitoes: - CDC light traps, indoor and outdoor, 30 randomly chosen houses/month, houses sprayed with pyrethroids (Mean number (density) of adult <i>An. arabiensis</i>) - Human-landing catches, indoors and outdoors. 8 houses/month, two houses for four consecutive nights.

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	- Window exit traps-night	
Notes	<p>Continent: Africa Country: Ethiopia Urban or rural: Rural Transmission intensity: Low Transmission season(s): Rainy season Vectors: <i>An. arabiensis</i> and other <i>anophelines</i> Malaria parasite: <i>Pl. falciparum</i> Source of funding: NA Study included in the previous review: No. The previous review [3] reported differences in habitats between intervention and control at baseline-so the paper was excluded from the review.</p>	
Risk of bias [Robins-I]		
Outcome assessed	Secondary outcome: Density of adult mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Serious	1.1 Potential for confounding? Probably yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? No 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? No 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Probably yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? No
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No
Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? Probably no 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? Probably no
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? No

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		6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? No
Bias in selection of the reported result	Low	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? No 7.3 Different subgroups? No
Overall bias	Serious	
Outcome assessed	Primary outcome: Density of immature mosquitoes	
Bias	Authors' Judgment	Support for judgement
Bias due to confounding	Serious	1.1 Potential for confounding? Probably yes 1.4 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline confounding? No 1.6 Control for post-intervention variables? No 1.7 Appropriate analysis to control for baseline and time varying confounders? No
Bias in selection of participants into the study	Low	2.1 Selection of participants based on their characteristics? No 2.4 Start of follow up and intervention coincide? Probably yes
Bias in classification of interventions	Low	3.1 Intervention groups clearly defined? Yes 3.2 Information to define intervention groups recorded at start of intervention? Yes 3.3 Classification of intervention status affected by knowledge of outcome or risk of outcome? No
Bias due to deviations from intended interventions	Low	4.1 Deviations from intended intervention? No

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Bias due to missing data	Low	5.1 Outcome data available for all, or nearly all, participants? Probably yes 5.2 Participants excluded due to missing data on intervention status? Probably no 5.3 Participants excluded due to missing data on other variables? Probably no
Bias in measurement of outcomes	Low	6.1 Outcome measures have been influenced by knowledge of intervention? No 6.2 Outcome assessor aware of intervention received? Yes 6.3 Methods of outcome assessment comparable across groups? Yes 6.4 Systematic errors in measurement of outcome related to intervention? No
Bias in selection of the reported result	Low	Reported effect estimate likely to be selected on 7.1 Multiple outcome measurements? No 7.2 Multiple analyses? No 7.3 Different subgroups? No
Overall bias	Serious	

NA: not applicable, NI: no information

Characteristics of excluded studies

Study	Reason for exclusion
Amerasinghe1991 [1]	Study design did not match inclusion criteria, observational study
Balfour 1936 [2]	Unclear description of study design and intervention
Clark 2012 [3]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, Abstracts from Symposium
Clark 2013 [4]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, Abstracts from Symposium
Clark 2014 [5]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, Abstracts from Symposium
Cohnstaedt 2016 [6]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, Abstracts from Symposium
Cohnstaedt 2017 [7]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, Abstracts from Symposium
Frake 2017 [8]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, Master thesis
Gezie 2018 [9]	Study design did not match inclusion criteria, observational study
Jaleta 2013 [10]	Study design did not match inclusion criteria, cross-sectional study
Kibret 2014 [11]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, no intervention described
Kiszewski 2014 [12]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, no intervention described
Laporta 2019 [13]	Study design did not match inclusion criteria, Review

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Nasreen 2016 [14]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, no intervention described
Ohta 2014 [15]	Study design did not match inclusion criteria, modeling paper
Saxena 2014 [16]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria, no intervention described
Srivastava 2013 [17]	Intervention did not match inclusion criteria
Van Den Berg 2018 [18]	Duplicate publication of an included ongoing study

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